

Flexural Performance of Non-Loadbearing Blast-Resistant Precast Concrete Cladding Panels with Discrete Connections

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Abstract

Boundary conditions of non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding panels differ from monolithic cast-in-place walls by relying on discrete connections for attachment to the main structural system, typically at the floor diaphragms. When the panels are designed to resist far-field blast loading, discrete connections at the diaphragms are commonly idealized as horizontal lines of continuous support, with cladding panels are analyzed assuming vertical (primary) one-way flexural behavior. Two-way or horizontal (transverse) one-way flexural response can realistically occur with variations in reinforcement layout or connection spacing; however, these modes of flexural response are typically neglected in conventional design approaches but could severely limit a panel's flexural ductility and capacity. In this paper, a validated nonlinear finite element model is used to conduct a comprehensive parametric study of the flexural responses of solid non-loadbearing precast concrete façade panels with discrete connections subjected to uniform lateral (normal) pressure. Sensitivity of ultimate flexural capacity based on discrete boundary conditions is examined for different ratios of primary to transverse reinforcement as well as different vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios. Models with discrete connections were able to achieve a vertical

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20 mechanism by either decreasing the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal flexural capacity and/or
21 increasing the number of lateral connections (thereby reducing the horizontal span **between**
22 **connections**). For panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios near 1.0, a vertical-to-
23 horizontal flexural capacity ratio of 0.5 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism. For
24 panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios greater than 1.5, a vertical-to-horizontal
25 flexural capacity ratio **of 1.0** was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism.

26 **Keywords:** precast concrete; far-field blast resistance; two-way flexural behavior; discrete
27 connections

28 **1 Introduction**

29 A building façade provides the first line of defense in protecting occupants against exterior
30 blast threats. Blast hazards are typically bifurcated into two classifications: near-field (to which a
31 façade panel responds via breach and spalling) or far-field (for which a panel response is
32 characterized by flexure and shear). This paper addresses the response to far-field blast hazards,
33 which constitutes a majority of intentional or accidental hazards that are considered by current
34 blast resistant design standards for buildings [1,2]. Concrete panels are often chosen for blast
35 resistant building applications due to their mass and customizable strength and ductility. Precast
36 panels possess several advantages over cast-in-place concrete, including high quality control via
37 plant casting and rapid piecewise installation. Unlike cast-in-place concrete construction, precast
38 concrete panels are attached to the main structural system (typically at the floor diaphragms) using
39 discretely welded, bolted, or bearing connections. During the blast design process, a panel's
40 discrete connections along the floor diaphragm are often idealized as a continuous horizontal line
41 support as shown in Figure 1a and b. The panels are thereby designed to resist out-of-plane blast-
42 induced pressure loads by spanning one-way vertically between floors. The longitudinal

43 reinforcement running in the horizontal direction is thereby assumed to contribute little to the
44 panel's blast resistance and is often detailed to meet minimum reinforcement requirements (i.e. for
45 temperature and shrinkage) [3,4]. However, the flexural response of panels with discrete
46 connections to the floor diaphragm may not be constrained to the vertical direction depending on
47 the spacing and stiffness of the connections as well as the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal
48 reinforcement in the panel. Minimizing the number of discrete connections can reduce cost via
49 simpler fabrication and less installation labor, but too much spacing between the connections can
50 allow the formation of unexpected two-way or one-way horizontal flexural behavior. Flexure in
51 the horizontal direction may exhibit significantly less resistance than in the vertical direction if the
52 horizontal reinforcement was not explicitly designed to resist the blast loads. Two-way flexure can
53 provide greater resistance than one-way vertical bending, but the resulting increase in reaction
54 forces may overwhelm the connections (which would have been designed to resist smaller
55 reactions from a one-way vertical plastic mechanism).

56 This paper investigates the influence of discrete connection layouts and the ratio of vertical-
57 to-horizontal flexural resistance on the response of solid non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding
58 panels to uniform lateral (i.e. normal) pressure. The expected flexural resistance functions of these
59 panels are obtained via nonlinear finite element (FE) analyses and compared to those generated
60 using conventional one-way flexural design assumptions (which are commonly used as input for
61 generalized single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) blast calculations in current practice). The
62 numerical modeling undertaken in this study will focus on the following: (1) improve
63 understanding of the fundamental flexural response of realistically supported and reinforced
64 precast cladding panels, (2) provide guidance to designers regarding the governing mechanics of
65 these systems, and (3) inform the development of future experimental test programs on this topic.

66 Note that this study only addresses the response of solid precast panels (i.e. single wythe, without
67 a sandwiched insulation layer) with no openings for windows, doors, ventilation, etc. - those topics
68 will be the focus of future research.

69 **2 Background**

70 Precast cladding panels can be fabricated with a variety of geometric shapes and connection
71 arrangements. The panel geometry and connection layout are typically based on architectural
72 design (e.g. the layout of corners, windows, doors, and other openings in the façade), shipping or
73 erection limitations, and the location of available supports at floor diaphragms and other framing.
74 A generic solid precast wall panel is shown in Figure 1a with a one-story vertical span between
75 floor diaphragms and an approximate aspect ratio of 2. The panel is shown with a common layout
76 of six discrete connections that are capable of resisting lateral displacement. Since most non-
77 loadbearing façade panels are hung from the building, the top row of connections would be
78 accompanied by additional connections to carry the panel's self-weight.

79
 80 Figure 1. Representative single-story precast cladding panel: (a) with realistic discrete supports,
 81 (b) with idealized line supports at the floor diaphragms, and (c) as a SDOF model for dynamic
 82 blast resistant analysis.

83 **2.1 Standard Practice for Blast Resistant Design**

84 In current practice, blast resistant design is typically initiated after the wall panel has been
 85 designed for conventional loads associated with handling, storage, shipping, and service conditions
 86 (such as wind loading). Though some panels utilize prestressing strands to control cracking, most
 87 conventional designs rely on mild steel reinforcement (using either deformed bars or welded-wire
 88 mesh) as the primary resistor of blast-induced flexure. This study will therefore focus on panels
 89 that are reinforced with non-prestressed mild steel reinforcement – the effects of initial prestressing
 90 will be considered in future work. For blast-resistant design, a precast panel is typically analyzed
 91 assuming one-way vertical flexural response between the idealized continuous boundary
 92 conditions shown in Figure 1b at the floor diaphragms [5]. It is generally assumed that the presence
 93 of multiple connections along the top and bottom of the panel would minimize flexure in the
 94 horizontal direction and provide an equivalent “line” support to vertical flexure. Using these

95 assumptions, it is standard practice to utilize a SDOF analysis [6], illustrated in Figure 1c, to
96 dynamically assess the blast resistance of the component.

97 As shown in Figure 2, two types of discrete connections are typically used to support non-
98 loadbearing precast cladding components in current U.S. practice: bearing and tieback. Bearing
99 connections are designed to resist gravity loads without significant restraint to out-of-plane
100 demands. Tieback connections are used to resist out-of-plane lateral loading conditions such as
101 wind and blast demands. Some tieback connections are designed to accommodate temperature
102 changes by allowing movement in one or more directions in the plane of the panel. For example,
103 the slotted tieback connection in the lower right corner of Figure 2 allows translation in the vertical
104 direction. Some panel connection details for conventional loads may only have a small gap (~4
105 cm) between the inside face of the panel and the edge of the diaphragm slab or framing. In those
106 configurations, the panel may bear on the diaphragm after some initial horizontal bending,
107 subsequently encouraging the one-way vertical behavior (Figure 1b) that is commonly assumed in
108 current practice. However, tieback connections for blast resistance often have a larger gap, and
109 flexural bearing on the edge of the diaphragm cannot be reliably considered as a mode for inducing
110 one-way vertical bending given the uncertainty of the horizontal deflection at which gap closure
111 would be reached. This study therefore neglects the possibility of bearing on the diaphragm edge
112 due to horizontal bending. Future research is needed to examine the sensitivity of the panel's
113 flexural response to blast-induced bearing at the diaphragm edge (which may include a dynamic
114 "slamming" reaction) based on a potential range of gap magnitudes.

Figure 2. Typical cladding connections

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 116
 117 For blast resistant applications, non-loadbearing precast panels are commonly modeled as
 118 an SDOF system by transforming spatial variations of loads and distributed mass via a load-mass
 119 factor, K_{LM} , based on the normalized deflected shape. Typical SDOF approaches for blast resistant
 120 design assume that the flexural response of the element under blast loading will follow a static
 121 deflected shape using idealized boundary conditions [6]. The SDOF equation of motion can be
 122 solved considering the mass, M ; resistance function, $R(y(t))$; and the applied pressure-time history,
 123 $F(t)$. The resistance function can be determined based on material properties, cross-section
 124 geometry, span length, and boundary conditions. Using iterative analyses, the panel is designed to
 125 achieve a specified level of allowable damage when subjected to design-basis blast load(s). To
 126 absorb energy, the panels are typically designed to experience permanent deformations under the
 127 short-duration blast load. Subsequent design of the connections is based on either the equivalent
 128 static reaction force at the panel's ultimate capacity or the peak dynamic reaction force [5]. When
 129 precast wall panels with multiple discrete connections are designed for vertical flexure assuming

130 a line support at the floor diaphragms, the resulting ultimate capacity or peak dynamic reaction
131 force of the idealized SDOF model is typically distributed to the discrete connections according to
132 tributary area.

133 **2.2 *Blast Performance Metrics***

134 Most U.S. Government design standards for assessing the performance of a structural
135 component to intentional blast demands [7] have adopted response criteria for anti-terrorism and
136 force protection that were developed by the US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) [8]. Five
137 damage levels ranging from superficial (i.e. the element has no permanent visible damage) to
138 blowout (i.e. the element is completely overwhelmed) are correlated to empirically prescribed
139 component deformation limits. As discussed by Gombeda et al. [9], these response limits do not
140 directly capture material limit states and were developed based on visual observations from a suite
141 of blast test results. To account for the utilization of material capacity in response to blast loading,
142 Gombeda et al. [9] proposed alternative performance-based definitions of response limits based
143 on mechanical and material behavior milestones. The recommended response milestones, based
144 on similar milestones for permanent deformation under seismic loading [10], correspond to first
145 yield, half peak, three-quarters peak, and peak flexural capacity along the load-deformation
146 response of the panel.

147 Gombeda et al. [9] introduced these milestones for a one-way spanning non-loadbearing
148 precast panel using the line support boundary condition assumption shown previously in Figure
149 1b. Due to the idealized simple supports, such a panel exhibits an approximately bi-linear
150 resistance to lateral pressure in which peak capacity occurs in the intended span direction. Panels
151 with discrete connections may form an initial mechanism earlier in the load-deformation history
152 followed by a stable secondary mechanism. For example, the ultimate strength of a panel can be

153 reached due to initial two-way engagement of the panel, after which peak displacement is reached
154 at a lower capacity (i.e. in the descending branch of the panel's resistance function) once the
155 weaker of the two flexural directions progresses toward failure. For this reason, the peak
156 displacement of the panel is used to represent the peak milestone in this paper. Comparisons of
157 response limits for reinforced concrete flexural members according to USACE [8] and Gombeda
158 et al. [9] are shown in Table 1. Both sets of response criteria will be used later in this paper to
159 assess the flexural performance of panels with discrete connections.

160 Both sets of response limits are compatible with the generalized SDOF analysis approach,
161 in which the flexural strength, stiffness, and deformation ductility of an element under dynamic
162 loading are defined by its resistance function. In current practice, the SDOF approach is
163 traditionally conducted using simplified assumptions, including an elastic-perfectly-plastic (EPP)
164 resistance function, idealized boundary conditions, and nominal material properties. However, the
165 simplified EPP approach combined with the one-way vertical span assumption may lead to
166 inaccurate predictions of precast panel performance when discrete connections are used. As
167 discussed, the presence of discrete connections may complicate the actual deformation response
168 of the component if unexpected bi-directional deformation occurs. For example, a panel with
169 minimal reinforcement in the horizontal direction may result in a weaker mechanism orthogonal
170 to the assumed one-way vertical span, leading to reduced overall flexural resistance. Conversely,
171 bi-directional behavior that increases the panel's flexural resistance can reduce deformation and
172 damage but cause higher reaction forces, which can overcome the design capacity of the
173 connections.

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Table 1. Flexural response limits for non-loadbearing precast concrete panels

Element Description	Damage Level	Response Limits		
		PDC [8]	Gombeda et al. [9]	Response Limit Used
Reinforced concrete flexural members with no shear reinforcing and tension membrane	Superficial			
	B1	$\mu=1$	First yield of reinforcement	First yield of reinforcement
	Moderate			
	B2	$\square=2^\circ$	1/2 Peak resistance	1/2 Peak displacement
	Heavy			
	B3	$\square=5^\circ$	3/4 Peak resistance	3/4 Peak displacement
	Hazardous			
	B4	$\square=10^\circ$	Peak resistance	Peak displacement
Blowout				

176 2.3 Review of Recent Experimental Tests

177 Recent blast tests of non-loadbearing precast panels have integrated the one-way flexure
178 assumption into their test protocols by providing full edge bearing support at either end of the
179 tested panels [3,11–13]. Several recent studies [14,15] have performed large scale blast tests of
180 non-loadbearing precast wall panels that are supported with discrete connections; however, the
181 connection spacing was much smaller than the primary panel span, and the panels therefore
182 responded primarily in one-way bending as assumed in Figure 1b. Despite this, the resulting crack
183 patterns near the discrete connections (for example, at the bottom connections in **Error!**
184 **Reference source not found.**a [14,15]) did show some mild bi-directional response due to the
185 presence of the discrete connections. This behavior is also observed in other experimentally tested
186 panels with point supports when subjected to out-of-plane loading [16,17]. To date, bi-directional
187 response for realistic discrete connection spacing in full-scale cladding panels has not been directly

188 examined. Blast testing on concrete panels to examine two-way flexural response has
189 predominantly provided continuous bearing support to all four edges [18,19] rather than using
190 discrete connections.

191 The previous tests by Cramsey and Naito [14] and Naito et al. [15] showed that discrete
192 connections designed for conventional design loads do not perform well when subjected to blast
193 demands. Weld fracture within tieback connections, buckling of tieback plates, and punching shear
194 failure of steel stud embed plates in the concrete panels can occur when these connections are not
195 properly detailed for blast design requirements as shown in Naito et al. [20] (**Error! Reference**
196 **source not found.**b-e). Blast-induced reaction loads will be heavily influenced by the governing
197 flexural mechanics and plastic mechanism in either one-way (vertical or horizontal) or two-way
198 bending due to the presence of discrete connections and varying bi-directional reinforcement.

199
200 Figure 3. Post-test photos of precast panels subjected to blast loading: (a) front and back face
201 [14,15], and (b-e) damage to different types of connections [20]

202 3 Model Validation

203 This study relies on fundamental mechanics (via validated FE models) to develop panel
204 resistance functions that capture realistic response mechanisms and damage milestones for a panel
205 with discrete connections. These load-displacement relationships could ultimately be implemented
206 into the aforementioned dynamic SDOF analysis methodology for blast resistant design. The focus
207 of this paper is the sensitivity of these load-displacement relationships to the presence of discrete
208 connections. Implementation of these resistance function in an “enhanced” SDOF approach, which
209 can be performed using the approach proposed previously by Gombeda et al. [9], will be the subject
210 of future research.

211 The out-of-plane flexural performance of non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding panels
212 with discrete connections is examined via nonlinear FE modeling in ABAQUS [21]. Before
213 conducting a parametric study, the FE modeling approach is validated using load-deformation
214 results from previous experimental tests of both one-way and two-way spanning non-load bearing
215 reinforced concrete panels. The nonlinear resistance function for each panel was obtained using
216 the ABAQUS/Explicit analysis module, which can facilitate numerical stability with non-linear
217 material models for concrete and steel reinforcement. Quasi-static analyses were conducted using
218 a relatively slow loading rate to allow for gradual ramping of applied loads with negligible inertial
219 effects. Quasi-static behavior was verified by insuring that a maximum ratio of kinetic-to-strain
220 energies of 10% is maintained throughout the analysis [21]. The panel is modeled using a three-
221 dimensional homogenous shell element (type S4) which also allows for transverse shear
222 deformations. The S4 element automatically assigns the type of shell as either thick or thin. Thick
223 shell theory is considered when the panel thickness-to-span length ratio is larger than 1/15, and
224 Kirchoff thin shell theory is used for smaller ratios [21]. All panels examined in this study met the

225 latter requirement for thin shell behavior. Steel reinforcement is defined as a smeared uniaxial
226 layer at a user-defined depth in the shell element. The nonlinear behavior through the thickness of
227 a component is defined by introducing integration points to calculate section properties [21].
228 Simpson's rule is used for the shell section integration with around eleven integration points
229 through the thickness of the section, to capture non-linear behavior [21]. The shell elements were
230 meshed with an approximately square discretization with maximum edge dimension of 10.16 cm
231 (4 in). Both the number of integration points and the mesh size were determined to be sufficient
232 via a preliminary convergence study using several of the validation cases.

233 Concrete behavior is modeled using a concrete damage plasticity (CDP) model with a
234 dilation angle of 36° and eccentricity of 0.1 [21]. The ratio of biaxial, σ_{b0} , to uniaxial compressive
235 strength, σ_{c0} , is taken as 1.16 [21]. A yield function is used to account for concrete's different
236 response in tension and compression. The ratio of the tensile to compression meridian that defines
237 the yield function in the deviatoric plane, K_c , was assumed as 2/3 [21]. The uniaxial stress-strain
238 relationship for concrete in tension is defined as linear elastic up to the modulus of rupture, after
239 which a smooth descending branch accounts for the progression of micro-cracking and mitigates
240 numerical instability. This softening model is populated using Equation 1 per Belarbi and Hsu [22]
241 where f_t and ε_t are the maximum tensile strength and corresponding strain; f_{cr} and ε_{cr} are the
242 modulus of rupture and corresponding strain; and n represents the rate of weakening (taken as 0.6).
243 Unless the value is provided in the experimental data, modulus of rupture was calculated using
244 Equation 2 [23], where f'_c is the concrete compressive strength (in MPa) and λ is the aggregate
245 modification factor (taken as 1.0 for normalweight concrete).

246 The Popovics model [24] is used to define the uniaxial stress-strain relationship for
247 concrete in compression. The modulus of elasticity, E_c , for concrete (in MPa) was calculated using

248 Equation 3 [23], where γ_c (the unit weight for concrete) is assumed to be 22.78 kN/m³ (145 pcf)
 249 across all panel cases. Where needed, the elastic stiffness of the finite element model is calibrated
 250 to the initial stiffness of the experimental test specimen by multiplying the elastic modulus by an
 251 adjustment factor α . The value of α is bounded by the limits of the scatter in the experimental
 252 measurements that provide the basis for the ACI 318 elastic modulus design equation [25], which
 253 is shown below in Equation 3 [23]. This expression will be used for the parametric study later in
 254 this paper.

$$f_t = f_{cr} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{cr}}{\varepsilon_t} \right)^n \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$f_{cr} = 0.7\lambda\sqrt{f'_c} \quad (\text{in MPa}) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$E_c = \alpha \cdot 0.043 \gamma_c^{1.5} \sqrt{f'_c} \quad (\text{in MPa}) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

255 The FE modeling approach is validated against the results of four experimental studies that
 256 examined the semi-static response of reinforced concrete panels to out-of-plane flexural loading
 257 with no applied in-plane loading:

- 258 • Gombeda et al. [26] evaluated the behavior of one-way solid reinforced concrete panels with
 259 varying reinforcement subjected to a uniform out-of-plane pressure loading.
- 260 • Cashell et al. [27] examined the response of a two-way slab with continuous edge supports
 261 subjected to out-of-plane point loads that were uniformly spaced and of uniform magnitude.
- 262 • Both McNeice [16] and Sakka and Gilbert [17] examined the behavior of a two-way panel with
 263 point supports.

264 Figure 4 illustrates the experimental setup and cross-sections of each test specimen. Material
 265 properties for all tests are summarized in Table 2. The steel reinforcement stress-strain model used
 266 by Gombeda et al. [28] was obtained via tensile tests of mild steel reinforcement that were
 267 performed during that experimental program. Since similar data is not available for the other three

268 studies, their stress-strain relationships were conservatively assumed to be bilinear with an elastic-
 269 hardening response. The elastic modulus for steel reinforcement is assumed to be 200 GPa (29000
 270 ksi) for all cases. The properties for steel (such as yield stress, f_{sy} , and the tensile stress, f_{su} , and
 271 strain, ϵ_{su}) as well as the properties for concrete (such as compressive strength, f'_c , modulus of
 272 elasticity, E_c , and ultimate strain, ϵ_{cu}) are also summarized in Table 2. The concrete modulus of
 273 elasticity for Gombeda et al.[28], Cashell et al. [27], and McNeice [16] were initially calculated
 274 using Equation 3 and then calibrated to match the experimentally measured stiffness of the whole
 275 panel. As a result, the elastic moduli for these three cases were modified by an α -factor of 2/3. The
 276 concrete elastic modulus for Sakka and Gilbert [17] was directly provided in the test summary.
 277 The ultimate strain for concrete is calculated as a function of the modulus of elasticity and ultimate
 278 compressive strength per the Popovics model [24].

279 Table 2. Material properties of experimental specimens used for FE validation

Experiment	CONCRETE				STEEL		
	E_c (GPa)	f'_c (MPa)	ϵ_{cu} (%)	f_{cr} (MPa)	f_{sy} (MPa)	f_{su} (MPa)	ϵ_{su} (%)
Gombeda et al.[28]	22.35*	49.11	0.30**	3.78*	476	969	10.8
Cashell et at. [27]	19.0*	35.52	0.28**	3.10	550	589	2.5
McNeice [16]	19.89*	38.92	0.28**	3.37*	345	517*	10.0*
Sakka and Gilbert [17]	29.20	44.30	0.29**	3.61	600	641	2.2

*Assumed value based on ACI 318 [23]; not provided by the test summary

**Assumed value based on the Popovics model [24]; not provided by the test summary

Figure 4. Schematic of experimental specimens (dimensions in cm) tested by (a) Gombeda et al.[28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16] and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]

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The FE results, experimental response, and component-specific milestones (see Table 1) for the four validation cases are plotted in Figure 5. The resistance, corresponding to the applied pressure on the panel, is plotted against the midpoint (i.e. maximum) displacement of each panels. The FE model predictions show good agreement with the experimentally measured response. IN particular, the peak displacement at flexural failure for the models of Gombeda et al. [28] and Sakka and Gilbert [17] closely match the experimental data. Marginal discrepancies are observed in the FE failure displacements for Cashell et al. [27] and McNeice [16], most likely due to the unavoidable use of assumed material properties. However, the computational resistance at peak is generally conservative relative to experimental data for all cases.

The FE deflected shapes for the four validation cases are presented in Figure 6. Note that for two of the specimens (Figure 6c and d), only a quarter of the panel is shown due to symmetry in both directions. The FE model's deflected shape at peak milestone for Sakka and Gilbert [17]

295 is also compared with deformation contours captured during experimental testing and compares
 296 well to the results of the FE model as shown in Figure 6d. These results demonstrate the ability of
 297 this modeling approach to capture realistic mechanics of reinforced concrete panels.

298 (a)

(b)

299 (c)

(d)

300 Figure 5. Comparison of FE resistance functions with experimental test data from (a) Gombeda
 301 et al. [28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16], and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]

302 Figure 6. Deflected shapes (all dimensions in cm) of FE models representing (a) Gombeda et al.
 303 [28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16] and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]
 304

305 **4 Parametric Studies**

306 The validated FE model is used to examine changes in the flexural resistance functions and
 307 limit states of blast-resistant cladding panels due to varying discrete connection arrangements and
 308 cross-section design parameters. The parametric study is based on a generic prototype wall panel
 309 measuring 9.14 m (30 ft.) long by 4.57 m (15 ft.) tall (i.e. one story height per Figure 1a) with a
 310 thickness of 15.24 cm (6 in.). The wall panel is designed for conventional loads including wind,
 311 stripping, shipping/handling, and erection in accordance with the PCI Design Handbook [5]. The
 312 geometries and cross-section details of the panel are shown in Figure 7. The vertical bar size is not
 313 labeled because the reinforcement ratio in that direction is varied as part of the parametric study.
 314 The vertical reinforcement of the baseline prototype panel, designed for conventional loads,
 315 consists of #13 Grade 420 (#4 Grade 60) bars spaced at 39.37 cm (15.5 in.) on center for both the
 316 top and bottom layers. Horizontal reinforcement is designed for shrinkage and temperature

317 requirements [23] and consists of #10 Grade 420 (#3 Grade 60) bars spaced at 45.7 cm (18.0 in.)
 318 on center.

319 Material properties used for the FE model in the parametric study are summarized in Table
 320 3, and example stress-strain models for concrete and steel are plotted in Figure 8a and b,
 321 respectively. The same concrete model used for the validation study (see Section **Error!**
 322 **Reference source not found.**) is implemented herein, and a typical compressive strength of 34.47
 323 MPa (5000 psi) is assumed in all cases. The stress-strain relationship for steel reinforcement is
 324 based on tensile test data from Gombeda et al. [28] and is scaled to match the minimum
 325 requirements for yield strength, tensile strength, and ultimate tensile strain per ASTM A615 [29].
 326 The conventionally assumed elastic-perfectly-plastic stress-strain design curve for steel
 327 reinforcement [1] is also shown in Figure 8b for comparison.

328
 329 Figure 7. Generic precast panel configuration (all dimensions in cm) for parametric evaluation

330 Table 3. Material properties of the parametric FE models,

CONCRETE				STEEL		
E_c (GPa)	f'_c (MPa)	ϵ_{cu} (%)	f_{cr} (MPa)	f_{sy} (MPa)	f_{su} (MPa)	ϵ_{su} (%)
28.09	34.47	0.18	3.66	413.69	620.53	9.0

331 (a) (b)
 332 Figure 8. Stress-strain relationships for (a) concrete and (b) reinforcing steel used in the
 333 validation and parametric FE models

334 **4.1 Varying Connection Spacing**

335 The panels are analyzed with six (6DC) and eight (8DC) evenly spaced discrete
 336 connections as shown in Figure 9 – both of these configurations are commonly used in precast
 337 construction. Also shown are the idealized spans and boundary conditions for one-way SDOF
 338 calculations of blast resistance in the vertical ($w1$) and horizontal ($w2$) flexural directions [30].
 339 Similar to Figure 1b, the idealized boundary conditions in Figure 9 are assumed as continuous
 340 supports that run through all connections in the same vertical or horizontal line (i.e. the connections
 341 are often assumed in practice to provide adequate stiffness across these lines such that the idealized
 342 boundary condition can be reasonably applied). Using the validated FE approach, models of the
 343 discrete connection configurations will be compared to those using the idealized one-way flexural
 344 assumptions for the vertical and horizontal axis directions to evaluate the applicability of the
 345 idealized approach.

346
347 Figure 9. Variation in discrete connection spacing (units in cm) for parametric study

348 **4.2 Varying Ultimate Flexural Resistance in the Vertical Direction**

349 Table 4 shows the variations of bi-directional ultimate flexural capacity that are considered
350 in this study. Reinforcement in the $w1$ direction is varied while $w2$ is held constant at 6.26 kPa
351 (0.91 psi) or 14.13 kPa (2.09 psi) (corresponding to the ACI 318 minimum for temperature and
352 shrinkage effects [23]) for both the 6DC and 8DC cases. Reinforcement ratio is calculated using
353 Equation 4 where A_s corresponds to the area of the extreme tension reinforcing steel; d is the
354 distance from the extreme concrete compression fiber to the center of the extreme tensile steel
355 reinforcement; and b is the bar spacing. Table 4 summarizes the reinforcement configurations
356 considered in this study. As shown in Figure 7, the doubly reinforced cross-section utilizes the
357 same rebar arrangements for the top and bottom layers. It is assumed that the precast concrete
358 walls in this study are exposed to weather and manufactured under controlled plant conditions, and
359 thus the clear cover for all rebar is set at 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) in accordance with ACI 318-14 [23].

360 As shown in Table 4, the range of vertical (primary) ultimate resistance is increased from
361 7.61 kPa to 52.31 kPa, thus increasing or “hardening” the panel’s lateral resistance per the idealized
362 vertical span assumption in Figure 1b. The nominal moment capacity and net tensile strain are
363 calculated via strain compatibility analysis considering both layers of reinforcement. The
364 reinforcement near the compression face is subjected to low levels of tension at nominal capacity

365 and is included in the flexural strength calculations for completeness but is neglected when
 366 calculating the reinforcement ratio since its contribution is low and most designers would not
 367 include it for simplicity. The reinforcement ratio is therefore computed using only the extreme
 368 tension steel. The lowest vertical ultimate resistance is chosen such that the ratio of the nominal,
 369 M_n , to cracking moment, M_{cr} , using gross section properties is slightly greater than 1. The largest
 370 vertical ultimate resistance corresponds to a net tensile strain, ϵ_t , equal to 0.005 (i.e. the lower limit
 371 for tension controlled sections in accordance with ACI 318-14 [23]) in the extreme tension
 372 reinforcement at the nominal flexural capacity.

373 Table 4. Matrix of vertical (primary) ultimate flexural resistance used for parametric study

Bar size	#10 (#3)	#13 (#4)	#13 (#4)	#16 (#5)	#16 (#5)
d (cm)	12.86	12.7	12.7	12.54	12.54
b (cm)	28.58	39.37	30.48	15.24	7.62
ρ (%)	0.19	0.25	0.33	1.04	2.09
ρ_T (%)	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
ϵ_t	0.040	0.030	0.023	0.007	0.005
M_n (kN-m)	136.61	177.45	225.0	522.94	938.4
M_n/M_{cr}	1.05	1.36	1.74	4.0	7.25
wI (kPa)	7.61	9.89	12.53	29.14	52.31
wI/w_2 (6DC)	1.22	1.58	2.00	4.66	8.36
wI/w_2 (8DC)	0.54	0.70	0.89	2.07	3.71

$$\rho = \frac{A_s}{b \cdot d} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

374 Figure 10 shows the correlation of net tensile strain with allowable support rotation for a
 375 one-way reinforced concrete wall panel at the critical response milestones per Gombeda et al [28].
 376 For higher values of ϵ_t (greater than 0.055), the cross-section behaves somewhat similarly to an
 377 unreinforced concrete cross-section, which exhibits a brittle failure mechanism limited by the
 378 tensile capacity of the concrete. Due to the shallow neutral axis depth, c , the small quantity of steel
 379 reinforcement rapidly accrues tensile strain prior to developing a fully-cracked section. This results
 380 in low ductility at all limit states as the peak flexural capacity is reached near the onset of flexural
 381 cracking. At ϵ_t just below 0.055, the maximum ductility is achieved via tension-controlled section

382 behavior while approaching the maximum theoretical utilization of the steel reinforcement. As ϵ_t
 383 continues to decrease, the likelihood of compression-controlled section behavior increases as the
 384 neutral axis depth continues to move downward, thus accruing strain in the extreme concrete
 385 compression fiber more rapidly than in the tension reinforcement. The section will experience
 386 concrete crushing before the tensile capacity of the reinforcement can be significantly utilized,
 387 resulting in decreased ductility. Several cross-sections with varying net tensile strain will be
 388 examined in this study to examine whether the aforementioned observations also apply to two-
 389 way spanning panels with discrete connections.

390
 391 Figure 10 - Critical limit states and dominant response mechanisms as a function of net tensile
 392 strain

393 4.3 Varying Connection Restraints

394 As shown previously in Figure 2, several different types of discrete connections are used
 395 to attach cladding panels to the structural system of a building, and these connections can be
 396 arranged to create a variety of boundary conditions for the panel. For example, tieback connections
 397 can be arranged to act as roller with no translational restraint in either the vertical or horizontal
 398 direction. The orthogonal non-roller direction could be idealized as either a pin or stiff translational

399 spring. In the parametric study to follow, three possible boundary condition variations are
 400 considered for the six connection (6DC) panel. BC1 is shown in Figure 11a where tieback
 401 connections are arranged to allow thermal expansion in the horizontal direction and resist
 402 translation in the vertical (primary) flexural direction. This case provides an idealized
 403 representation of the typical tieback orientation used in practice. In Figure 11b, BC2 shows a
 404 tieback orientation that instead allows expansion along the vertical axis. In Figure 11c, BC3 shows
 405 an idealized case where tieback connections would allow translation in both the vertical and
 406 horizontal directions (i.e. resembling a true simply supported panel). BC2 and BC3 represent
 407 boundary conditions that are less feasible in practice but are included here to examine the influence
 408 of in-plane connection restraint. Note that for all assumed boundary conditions, additional bearing
 409 connections along the top of the panel would be installed to support the gravity loads. It is
 410 commonly assumed that the bearing connections would not influence the response of the panel to
 411 lateral loading; however, their participation in lateral resistance could be a consideration for future
 412 research on this topic.

413
 414 Figure 11. Idealized support conditions for parametric FE analysis of 6DC panels (units in cm)

415 **5 Results**

416 The parametric analyses are labeled as follows: the first parameter denotes the number of
 417 discrete connections in a panel (6DC and 8DC as shown in Figure 9); the second parameter shows
 418 the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal ultimate resistance (e.g. $w1/w2 = 1.58$ for 6DC as shown in Table
 419 4); and the third parameter denotes the type of boundary conditions (BC1, BC2 and BC3 as shown

420 in Figure 11). The initial focus will evaluate the out-of-plane flexural performance of the 6DC
421 panels, which represent the most common connection configuration used in practice. Then the
422 analyses will evaluate the out-of-plane flexural performance of panels with 8DC.

423 **5.1 Panels with Six Discrete Connections (6DC)**

424 *5.1.1 Connection rotational stiffness*

425 Note that all lateral connections to this point have been represented in the FE model as a
426 translational restraint (with no rotational restraint) at a single node. Connections in precast
427 cladding construction are conventionally fabricated by embedding plates in the inside surface of
428 the panel via cast-in steel studs or other mechanical or post-installed anchorages. Although
429 connections are often idealized as a point support in design models, the true physical size of the
430 plate embed may provide a small amount of localized rotational resistance in addition to lateral
431 resistance. Selective preliminary analyses were performed prior to the full parametric study with
432 lateral connections represented with translational restraint at either one node or at four neighboring
433 nodes (i.e. assuming an embed plate size of 10.16 cm by 10.16 cm (4 in by 4 in)). The idealized 4-
434 node restraint was used to represent an upper bound for the development of localized moment
435 resistance by eliminating connection rotation at the shell element surrounded by the four supported
436 nodes (i.e. representing a “rotationally rigid” embed plate). This numerical representation provides
437 much higher rotational stiffness than a realistic embed connection, which would have low
438 rotational stiffness at its interface with the bolts or welded plates that connect the embed to the
439 structural system. The analysis is performed only for the conventionally designed panel with 6DC
440 and BC1 ($6DC-w1/w2=2-BC1$) for preliminary evaluation. A fourth parameter is added to the
441 reference labeling system for “large” boundary conditions (LBC) to identify cases in which the
442 connections are represented with a 4-node lateral restraint instead of single node lateral restraint.

443 Figure 12a compares the plots of semi-static load-displacement response obtained from FE
 444 analysis of the $6DC-w1/w2=2-BC1$ model with single node and 4-node (LBC) connections. The
 445 plotted lateral displacement represents the maximum overall panel displacement measured
 446 approximately midway between the connections as shown in Figure 12b. The component-specific
 447 limit states (see Table 1) are also plotted for each case. As expected, the presence of additional
 448 rotational restraint at the connections provides $\sim 25\%$ more out-of-plane flexural resistance and
 449 slightly greater deformation ductility. As noted previously, realistic connections will exhibit low
 450 rotational stiffnesses that more closely resemble the single supported node; therefore, the
 451 remaining analyses are conservatively conducted using the point support simplification.

452 (a) (b)
 453 Figure 12. Preliminary evaluation of connection rotational stiffness: (a) resistance functions and
 454 (b) deflected panel shapes with single node and “large” 4-node lateral supports (units in cm)

455 5.1.2 Resistance functions and deflected shapes for 6DC

456 Resistance functions and deflected shapes are obtained using the validated FE model for
 457 all 6DC configurations (see Table 4 and Figure 9a) for all three boundary conditions (BC1, BC2
 458 and BC3 as shown in Figure 11). Figure 13 shows the deflected shape of each case at the peak

459 displacement limit state. Figure 14a plots the resulting resistance functions as out-of-plane pressure
460 versus maximum displacement. Figure 14b normalizes the y-axis of these plots relative to the
461 maximum flexural resistance of the vertical w/l direction assuming the idealized horizontal line
462 connections (Figure 1b) per conventional design practice. Component-specific limit states and
463 prescriptive antiterrorism response limits for a flexural reinforced concrete member (with no shear
464 reinforcement and without tension membrane action [8]) are plotted as vertical dashed lines B1
465 through B4 in Figure 14 for comparison.

466

467

Figure 13. Peak FE deflected shapes for the 6DC panels (units in cm)

468 (a)

469 (b)

470 Figure 14. Out-of-plane flexural resistance of the 6DC panels: (a) load-displacement resistance
471 functions and (b) normalized to $w1$

472 For BC1 (which is most representative of current practice), flexural behavior at peak
473 displacement was governed by the weaker reinforcement in the horizontal ($w2$) direction for all
474 $w1/w2$ ratios that were considered. As a result, all cases with BC1 exhibit similar deformation at
475 peak since the horizontal reinforcement remained unchanged. Peak displacements for BC3 (with
476 no in-plane translational restraint at the connections) are almost identical to those for BC1, with
477 only the smallest $w1/w2$ ratios showing minor signs of two-way bending. If the tieback connections
478 instead allow vertical in-plane translation and restrain the horizontal translation (BC2), the flexural
479 capacity becomes governed by the vertical reinforcement if $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$. As shown in both Figure
480 13 and Figure 14, achieving a mechanism in the vertical direction enables increased deformation

481 ductility versus the horizontal mechanisms. With further increases in vertical reinforcement, the
482 BC2 connection configuration will also exhibit a horizontal mechanism with lower ductility, as
483 was shown for BC1 and BC3.

484 As shown in Figure 14, BC2 cases with $w1/w2$ of 1.58 and 2.0 achieved by far the largest
485 peak ductility, with peak displacements extending past the conventional B4 response limit to
486 achieve “blowout” damage per the prescribed PDC blast design criteria in Table 1. The BC2 case
487 with $w1/w2 = 1.22$ has less ductility (nearly reaching the B3 response limit to achieve “hazardous”
488 damage) due to the decrease in vertical reinforcement. All other cases, governed by horizontal
489 bending, exhibited even less ductility and only surpassed the B2 response limit for “heavy”
490 damage. The horizontal direction not only has less reinforcement than the vertical direction but
491 also has stiffer boundary conditions due to its continuity across the vertical centerline between the
492 two horizontal spans (whereas the vertical span can rotate freely at both ends). A plastic
493 mechanism in the horizontal direction will therefore accrue more flexural strain for every
494 increment of deflection versus a mechanism in the vertical span.

495 When the flexural resistance is normalized by the conventionally assumed one-way
496 capacity in the vertical direction, Figure 14b shows that only BC2 panels with $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$ and
497 BC1 panels with $w1/w2 \leq 1.58$ are able to surpass the $w1$ peak flexural capacity. These BC2 cases
498 exceed the idealized $w1$ resistance since their flexural response is consistent with the vertical one-
499 way design expectation at lower $w1/w2$ ratios. The BC1 cases exceed the idealized $w1$ resistance
500 only because the $w2$ resistance at very low $w1/w2$ ratios is similar to that in the $w1$ direction.

501 5.1.3 Strain energy for 6DC

502 The dynamic resistance of a structural component can be characterized by computing the
503 strain energy as the area under the resistance function up to a response limit of interest. For

504 example, Figure 15 shows the strain energy of both the FE and the UFC resistance functions for a
 505 $6DC-w1/w2=1.58-BC1$ panel up to their respective B3 response limits (i.e. the transition between
 506 heavy and hazardous damage per Table 1). A model with larger value of strain energy for a
 507 particular damage state implies a higher resistance to impulsive blast-induced pressure loading.
 508 Figure 15 clearly shows that decreased ductility at similar damage states in the FE model versus
 509 its UFC counterpart can lead to marked decreases in calculated blast resistance.

511 Figure 15. Example strain energies calculated for (a) FE and (b) UFC resistance functions up to
 512 the B3 limit.
 513

514

515 Figure 16 compares the strain energy calculated using FE and UFC resistance functions for
 516 6DC panels with the BC1 and BC2 connection configurations. For the BC1 connections, Figure
 517 16a reveals that both approaches achieve similar strain energies at the B1 yield milestone for panels

518 with smaller $w1/w2$ ratios. For higher damage levels and larger $w1/w2$, the UFC approach (which
 519 assumes vertical one-way flexural behavior) overestimates the amount of strain energy for all BC1
 520 cases because the horizontal span direction controls the FE response (and thus reduces deformation
 521 ductility and peak capacity). In Figure 16b for the BC2 panels, the UFC results show similar
 522 overestimation of strain energy for damage states above B1 for larger $w1/w2$ ratios. At $w1/w2 \geq$
 523 4.66, the FE response is again controlled by the weaker horizontal spans, resulting in losses of
 524 available ductility and blast-resisting capacity. When the BC2 response achieves a vertical span
 525 condition for $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$, the UFC strain energy is conservative relative to the FE results, which
 526 accounts for realistic post-yield hardening as opposed to the UFC's elastic-perfectly-plastic
 527 assumption.

528
 529 Figure 16. Correlation of UFC and FE strain energies for 6DC panels with BC1 (solid scatter)
 530 and BC2 (open scatter)

531 *5.1.4 Reactions for 6DC*

532 The out-of-plane connection reactions from the FE panel models with 6DC and BC2 are
 533 compared to those based on the UFC approach [1], in which reaction demands, r , are based on the
 534 relative tributary area of the connection per Figure 1a and b via Equation 5:

$$r = w1 \times \text{Tributary Area}$$

$$\text{Equation 5}$$

535 Figure 17 plots the FE reaction for the discrete connections at both the edge and middle of the
 536 panel as a function of maximum panel displacement. A comparison between the UFC approach
 537 and the peak FE reaction of the middle connection is shown in Figure 17b. For $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$, the
 538 cases fall above the bisecting line, which demonstrates that the UFC approach underpredicts the
 539 expected peak reaction force due to its elastic-perfectly-plastic resistance assumption. At $w1/w2 \geq$
 540 4.66, the UFC reaction (based on the assumed vertical span response) is conservative since the FE
 541 response is controlled by the weaker horizontal spans and develops a smaller reaction. This
 542 comparison demonstrates that accurate determination of reaction design loads is depends on
 543 appropriate characterization of the mode of flexural resistance.

544 (a) (b)
 545 Figure 17. Connection reactions for 6DC-BC2 panels: (a) FE reactions versus displacement, and
 546 (b) correlation of FE and UFC reactions at the middle connection

547 5.2 Panels with Eight Discrete Connections (8DC)

548 5.2.1 Resistance functions and deflected shapes for 8DC

549 Increasing the number of discrete connections from six (6DC) to eight (8DC) per Figure
 550 9b with no change in reinforcement leads to smaller $w1/w2$ ratios than the 6DC panels as shown
 551 in Table 4 due to the reduced effective horizontal span length. Using BC1, the deformed shapes at

552 the peak displacement milestone are presented in Figure 18. Note that panel $8DC-w1/w2=3.71-$
 553 $BC1$ is not shown since it closely resembles the behavior observed for panel $8DC-w1/w2=2.07-$
 554 $BC1$. The FE resistance functions, shown in Figure 19, are normalized to the $w1$ UFC resistance
 555 and plotted against the maximum displacement at peak response. Similar to previous results, both
 556 figures show that configurations with higher $w1/w2$ result in plastic mechanisms in the horizontal
 557 direction while decreasing $w1/w2$ trends toward the preferred vertical floor-to-floor response
 558 mechanism. Specifically, the FE capacity is higher than the UFC resistance for all panels with
 559 $w1/w2$ less than 1.0. However, all FE resistance functions again develop comparable response
 560 limits at lower displacements than prescribed by the USACE criteria [8] in Table 1.
 561

562 Figure 18. FE model deflected shapes at peak displacement for 8DC-BC1 panels (units in cm)
 563

564 Figure 19. Resistance functions normalized to $w1$ for 8DC-BC1 panels
 565

566 5.2.2 Strain energy for 8DC

567 Figure 20 presents the relative strain energy calculated using the FE and UFC resistance
568 functions for panels with 8DC and BC1. Since the preferred vertical one-way mechanism occurs
569 in the FE models when $w1/w2 < 1.0$ (see Figure 18), these cases produce larger strain energy than
570 the UFC resistance functions at comparable response limits. These results are very similar to the
571 6DC panel cases and suggest that increasing only the vertical reinforcement can produce
572 significantly less strain energy (and thus less blast resistance) for discretely connected panels than
573 would be expected under the UFC approach. As will be shown in Section 6, accompanying
574 increases in horizontal reinforcement or the addition of other reinforcement detailing can help the
575 panel achieve a preferred ductile mechanism.

576 Figure 20. Correlation of the UFC approach and the FE strain energies for 8DC-BC1 panels

578 5.2.3 Reactions for 8DC

579 The reaction forces for both the edge and middle connections of the 8DC panels with BC1
580 are shown in Figure 21a. In Figure 21b, the FE maximum reaction is compared to the UFC $w1$
581 reaction as was done in Section 5.1.4 for the 6DC panels. The UFC approach again underestimates
582 peak reaction forces due to the use of realistic material hardening for panels that show the vertical

583 FE mechanism (for $w1/w2$ less than 1.0). For $w1/w2$ greater than 1.0, the transition of the FE
 584 flexural response from a stronger vertical to a weaker horizontal mechanism again produces
 585 smaller reaction forces versus the UFC approach.

586 (a) (b)
 587 Figure 21. Connection reactions for 8DC-BC1 panels: (a) FE reactions versus displacement, and
 588 (b) correlation of FE and UFC reactions at the middle connection

589 6 Alternative Detailing Strategies

590 6.1 Increased horizontal flexural resistance

591 The parametric study results showed that most of the panels with discrete connections and
 592 larger ratios of vertical-to-horizontal ultimate resistance exhibited a weaker flexural mechanism in
 593 the horizontal direction. Corresponding reductions in ductility lead to overestimation of the
 594 available strain energy (and thus the blast resistance) by the conventional UFC approach at
 595 comparable damage milestones. This section investigates the ratio of $w1/w2$ that will produce the
 596 preferred vertical flexural mechanism, using the 6DC panel with BC1 as a representative example.
 597 The vertical resistance ($w1$) is held constant per the $w1/w2=1.58$ 6DC case in Table 4, while the

598 horizontal reinforcement (and thus w_2) is increased beyond the minimum requirements for
 599 temperature and shrinkage.

600 Table 5 summarizes the new arrangements of horizontal reinforcement and the
 601 correspondingly updated ratios of w_1/w_2 . The deflected shapes at peak deformation are also shown
 602 in Figure 22. A transition from a dominant horizontal mechanism to bi-directional response is
 603 observed with decreasing w_1/w_2 . With a w_1/w_2 ratio of 0.5, the behavior of the panel approaches
 604 a one-way dominant mechanism in the intended vertical direction. Consistent with the deformed
 605 shapes, Figure 23 reveals improvements in both flexural capacity and ductility as w_1/w_2 decreases.
 606 Compared to the 8DC results (which achieved the ductile vertical mechanism at w_1/w_2 less than
 607 1.0), these results suggest that increasing the aspect ratio of vertical-to-horizontal span length by
 608 introducing more lateral connections may offer a more efficient solution for increasing the panel's
 609 blast resistance.

610 Table 5. Upgraded arrangements of horizontal (transverse) reinforcement

Cases	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.9-BC1$	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.77-BC1$	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.5-BC1$
Bar size and spacing	#10 @ 25.4 cm o.c.	#13 @ 39.37 cm o.c.	#13 @ 24.13 cm o.c.

611
 612 Figure 22. FE deflected shape at peak deformation for the 6DC-BC1 panels with enhanced
 613 horizontal reinforcement (units in cm)

614
615 Figure 23. Out-of-plane flexural resistance curve of the strengthened panel

616 **6.2 Enhanced edge reinforcement**

617 As an alternative to increasing the horizontal flexural reinforcement, localized regions of
618 edge reinforcement can be added to encourage the formation of the preferred vertical mechanism.
619 Additional edge reinforcement is often added to precast cladding panels in practice to enhance
620 structural integrity and reduce edge cracking in response to stripping and handling. In this case,
621 the additional edge reinforcement consists of two #16 Grade 420 (#5 Grade 60) bars in the
622 horizontal directional which are placed 10.16 cm (4.0 in.) above and below the centerlines of the
623 connections shown in Figure 7. Figure 24 shows the deformed shape at the peak milestone for this
624 panel and exhibits a much more prominent bi-directional response relative to the control panel.
625 Although this detailing strategy does not facilitate a pure one-way failure mechanism, the
626 resistance function demonstrates improvements in both flexural capacity and ductility as shown in
627 Figure 25 by engaging both flexural directions.

628
629

Figure 24. Peak deflected shapes for modified edge reinforcement panels

630
631

Figure 25. Resistance functions for panels with additional edge reinforcement

632 7 Summary and Conclusions

633 A numerical study of solid (i.e. non-insulated) precast concrete cladding panels was
 634 conducted to examine the influence of discrete connections on load-deformation response under
 635 out-of-plane loads. The study is conducted using a nonlinear finite element (FE) modeling
 636 approach that is validated against the results of four experimental studies by other researchers. The
 637 validated model was used to conduct a series of parametric studies which varied the number of
 638 discrete connections and the amount of reinforcement in both the vertical and horizontal directions.
 639 The numerical responses are also compared to standard blast design assumptions which
 640 incorporate nominal material properties and idealized elastic-perfectly-plastic response. Based on
 641 the results of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 642 • In current practice, panels with discrete connections are often designed for blast loading by
643 assuming one-way vertical flexural resistance between floor diaphragms. The horizontal spans
644 are designed with minimum reinforcement and are assumed to contribute little to the panels’
645 blast resistance. However, increasing only the vertical resistance in response to blast loading
646 requirements may induce an unexpected failure mechanism in the weaker horizontal direction
647 depending on the aspect ratio of vertical-to-horizontal span between connections, thus leading
648 to significant reductions in flexural capacity and ductility.
- 649 • Strain energies calculated for these horizontal mechanisms were significantly smaller than
650 those calculated for the conventional design approaches, which assumed the more ductile
651 vertical mechanism. Lower strain energy indicates lower blast resistance due to less energy
652 absorption in response to impulsive loading.
- 653 • Response limits corresponding to progressive states of flexural damage were calculated for
654 each panel configuration based on material properties and the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal
655 ultimate flexural resistance. Significant discrepancies between these tailored response limits
656 and current prescriptive blast response criteria were observed, especially for panels exhibiting
657 a premature weak direction failure mechanism. Many panel cases demonstrated significantly
658 less ductility at elevated levels of flexural damage compared with the prescriptive criteria.
- 659 • The FE models with discrete connections were able to achieve a vertical mechanism by either
660 decreasing the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal flexural capacity and/or increasing the number of
661 lateral connections (thereby reducing the horizontal span between these connections). For
662 panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios near 1.0, a vertical-to-horizontal flexural
663 capacity ratio of 0.5 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism. For panels with

664 vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios greater than 1.5, a vertical-to-horizontal flexural
665 capacity ratio of only 1.0 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism.

666 • Bi-directional flexural behavior and realistic material properties often result in reaction forces
667 significantly larger than predicted using the conventional assumption of vertical one-way
668 flexure. This implies that connections may need to be strengthened to realistically develop the
669 peak flexural capacity of the component.

670 • Localized additions of reinforcement near the panel edges can facilitate improvements in
671 flexural capacity and ductility for reinforcement and connection configurations that would
672 otherwise form the weak direction failure mechanism.

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Flexural Performance of Non-Loadbearing Blast-Resistant Precast Concrete Cladding Panels with Discrete Connections

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Flexural capacity of precast concrete panels with discrete connections is examined.
- Panels designed using current practice may exhibit unexpected failure mechanisms.
- Unexpected failure mechanisms may lead to major reductions in panel capacity.
- Alternate design strategies for mitigating the unexpected mechanisms are presented.

Flexural Performance of Non-Loadbearing Blast-Resistant Precast Concrete Cladding Panels with Discrete Connections

Omar M. Alawad^{1,*}, Matthew J. Gombeda², Spencer E. Quiel³, Clay J. Naito⁴

Abstract

Boundary conditions of non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding panels differ from monolithic cast-in-place walls by relying on discrete connections for attachment to the main structural system, typically at the floor diaphragms. When the panels are designed to resist far-field blast loading, discrete connections at the diaphragms are commonly idealized as horizontal lines of continuous support, with cladding panels analyzed assuming vertical (primary) one-way flexural behavior. Two-way or horizontal (transverse) one-way flexural response can realistically occur with variations in reinforcement layout or connection spacing; however, these modes of flexural response are typically neglected in conventional design approaches but could severely limit a panel's flexural ductility and capacity. In this paper, a validated nonlinear finite element model is used to conduct a comprehensive parametric study of the flexural responses of solid non-loadbearing precast concrete façade panels with discrete connections subjected to uniform lateral (normal) pressure. Sensitivity of ultimate flexural capacity based on discrete boundary conditions is examined for different ratios of primary to transverse reinforcement as well as different vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios. Models with discrete connections were able to achieve a vertical

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20 mechanism by either decreasing the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal flexural capacity and/or
21 increasing the number of lateral connections (thereby reducing the horizontal span between
22 connections). For panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios near 1.0, a vertical-to-
23 horizontal flexural capacity ratio of 0.5 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism. For
24 panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios greater than 1.5, a vertical-to-horizontal
25 flexural capacity ratio of 1.0 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism.

26 **Keywords:** precast concrete; far-field blast resistance; two-way flexural behavior; discrete
27 connections

28 **1 Introduction**

29 A building façade provides the first line of defense in protecting occupants against exterior
30 blast threats. Blast hazards are typically bifurcated into two classifications: near-field (to which a
31 façade panel responds via breach and spalling) or far-field (for which a panel response is
32 characterized by flexure and shear). This paper addresses the response to far-field blast hazards,
33 which constitutes a majority of intentional or accidental hazards that are considered by current
34 blast resistant design standards for buildings [1,2]. Concrete panels are often chosen for blast
35 resistant building applications due to their mass and customizable strength and ductility. Precast
36 panels possess several advantages over cast-in-place concrete, including high quality control via
37 plant casting and rapid piecewise installation. Unlike cast-in-place concrete construction, precast
38 concrete panels are attached to the main structural system (typically at the floor diaphragms) using
39 discretely welded, bolted, or bearing connections. During the blast design process, a panel's
40 discrete connections along the floor diaphragm are often idealized as a continuous horizontal line
41 support as shown in Figure 1a and b. The panels are thereby designed to resist out-of-plane blast-
42 induced pressure loads by spanning one-way vertically between floors. The longitudinal

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115 43 reinforcement running in the horizontal direction is thereby assumed to contribute little to the
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117 44 panel's blast resistance and is often detailed to meet minimum reinforcement requirements (i.e. for
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119 45 temperature and shrinkage) [3,4]. However, the flexural response of panels with discrete
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121 46 connections to the floor diaphragm may not be constrained to the vertical direction depending on
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123 47 the spacing and stiffness of the connections as well as the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal
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125 48 reinforcement in the panel. Minimizing the number of discrete connections can reduce cost via
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127 49 simpler fabrication and less installation labor, but too much spacing between the connections can
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129 50 allow the formation of unexpected two-way or one-way horizontal flexural behavior. Flexure in
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131 51 the horizontal direction may exhibit significantly less resistance than in the vertical direction if the
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133 52 horizontal reinforcement was not explicitly designed to resist the blast loads. Two-way flexure can
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135 53 provide greater resistance than one-way vertical bending, but the resulting increase in reaction
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137 54 forces may overwhelm the connections (which would have been designed to resist smaller
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139 55 reactions from a one-way vertical plastic mechanism).
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143 56 This paper investigates the influence of discrete connection layouts and the ratio of vertical-
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145 57 to-horizontal flexural resistance on the response of solid non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding
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147 58 panels to uniform lateral (i.e. normal) pressure. The expected flexural resistance functions of these
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149 59 panels are obtained via nonlinear finite element (FE) analyses and compared to those generated
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151 60 using conventional one-way flexural design assumptions (which are commonly used as input for
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153 61 generalized single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) blast calculations in current practice). The
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155 62 numerical modeling undertaken in this study will focus on the following: (1) improve
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157 63 understanding of the fundamental flexural response of realistically supported and reinforced
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159 64 precast cladding panels, (2) provide guidance to designers regarding the governing mechanics of
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161 65 these systems, and (3) inform the development of future experimental test programs on this topic.
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171 66 Note that this study only addresses the response of solid precast panels (i.e. single wythe, without
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173 67 a sandwiched insulation layer) with no openings for windows, doors, ventilation, etc. - those topics
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175 68 will be the focus of future research.
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178 69 **2 Background**

180 70 Precast cladding panels can be fabricated with a variety of geometric shapes and connection
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182 71 arrangements. The panel geometry and connection layout are typically based on architectural
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184 72 design (e.g. the layout of corners, windows, doors, and other openings in the façade), shipping or
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186 73 erection limitations, and the location of available supports at floor diaphragms and other framing.
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188 74 A generic solid precast wall panel is shown in Figure 1a with a one-story vertical span between
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190 75 floor diaphragms and an approximate aspect ratio of 2. The panel is shown with a common layout
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192 76 of six discrete connections that are capable of resisting lateral displacement. Since most non-
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194 77 loadbearing façade panels are hung from the building, the top row of connections would be
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196 78 accompanied by additional connections to carry the panel's self-weight.
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80 Figure 1. Representative single-story precast cladding panel: (a) with realistic discrete supports,
81 (b) with idealized line supports at the floor diaphragms, and (c) as a SDOF model for dynamic
82 blast resistant analysis.

83 2.1 Standard Practice for Blast Resistant Design

84 In current practice, blast resistant design is typically initiated after the wall panel has been
85 designed for conventional loads associated with handling, storage, shipping, and service conditions
86 (such as wind loading). Though some panels utilize prestressing strands to control cracking, most
87 conventional designs rely on mild steel reinforcement (using either deformed bars or welded-wire
88 mesh) as the primary resistor of blast-induced flexure. This study will therefore focus on panels
89 that are reinforced with non-prestressed mild steel reinforcement – the effects of initial prestressing
90 will be considered in future work. For blast-resistant design, a precast panel is typically analyzed
91 assuming one-way vertical flexural response between the idealized continuous boundary
92 conditions shown in Figure 1b at the floor diaphragms [5]. It is generally assumed that the presence
93 of multiple connections along the top and bottom of the panel would minimize flexure in the
94 horizontal direction and provide an equivalent “line” support to vertical flexure. Using these

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283 95 assumptions, it is standard practice to utilize a SDOF analysis [6], illustrated in Figure 1c, to
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285 96 dynamically assess the blast resistance of the component.
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287 97 As shown in Figure 2, two types of discrete connections are typically used to support non-
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289 98 loadbearing precast cladding components in current U.S. practice: bearing and tieback. Bearing
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291 99 connections are designed to resist gravity loads without significant restraint to out-of-plane
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293 100 demands. Tieback connections are used to resist out-of-plane lateral loading conditions such as
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295 101 wind and blast demands. Some tieback connections are designed to accommodate temperature
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297 102 changes by allowing movement in one or more directions in the plane of the panel. For example,
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299 103 the slotted tieback connection in the lower right corner of Figure 2 allows translation in the vertical
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301 104 direction. Some panel connection details for conventional loads may only have a small gap (~4
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303 105 cm) between the inside face of the panel and the edge of the diaphragm slab or framing. In those
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305 106 configurations, the panel may bear on the diaphragm after some initial horizontal bending,
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307 107 subsequently encouraging the one-way vertical behavior (Figure 1b) that is commonly assumed in
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309 108 current practice. However, tieback connections for blast resistance often have a larger gap, and
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311 109 flexural bearing on the edge of the diaphragm cannot be reliably considered as a mode for inducing
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313 110 one-way vertical bending given the uncertainty of the horizontal deflection at which gap closure
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315 111 would be reached. This study therefore neglects the possibility of bearing on the diaphragm edge
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317 112 due to horizontal bending. Future research is needed to examine the sensitivity of the panel's
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319 113 flexural response to blast-induced bearing at the diaphragm edge (which may include a dynamic
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321 "slamming" reaction) based on a potential range of gap magnitudes.
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Figure 2. Typical cladding connections

For blast resistant applications, non-loadbearing precast panels are commonly modeled as an SDOF system by transforming spatial variations of loads and distributed mass via a load-mass factor, K_{LM} , based on the normalized deflected shape. Typical SDOF approaches for blast resistant design assume that the flexural response of the element under blast loading will follow a static deflected shape using idealized boundary conditions [6]. The SDOF equation of motion can be solved considering the mass, M ; resistance function, $R(y(t))$; and the applied pressure-time history, $F(t)$. The resistance function can be determined based on material properties, cross-section geometry, span length, and boundary conditions. Using iterative analyses, the panel is designed to achieve a specified level of allowable damage when subjected to design-basis blast load(s). To absorb energy, the panels are typically designed to experience permanent deformations under the short-duration blast load. Subsequent design of the connections is based on either the equivalent static reaction force at the panel's ultimate capacity or the peak dynamic reaction force [5]. When precast wall panels with multiple discrete connections are designed for vertical flexure assuming

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395 130 a line support at the floor diaphragms, the resulting ultimate capacity or peak dynamic reaction
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397 131 force of the idealized SDOF model is typically distributed to the discrete connections according to
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402 133 **2.2 Blast Performance Metrics**

404 134 Most U.S. Government design standards for assessing the performance of a structural
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406 135 component to intentional blast demands [7] have adopted response criteria for anti-terrorism and
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408 136 force protection that were developed by the US Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) [8]. Five
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410 137 damage levels ranging from superficial (i.e. the element has no permanent visible damage) to
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412 138 blowout (i.e. the element is completely overwhelmed) are correlated to empirically prescribed
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414 139 component deformation limits. As discussed by Gombeda et al. [9], these response limits do not
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416 140 directly capture material limit states and were developed based on visual observations from a suite
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418 141 of blast test results. To account for the utilization of material capacity in response to blast loading,
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420 142 Gombeda et al. [9] proposed alternative performance-based definitions of response limits based
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422 143 on mechanical and material behavior milestones. The recommended response milestones, based
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424 144 on similar milestones for permanent deformation under seismic loading [10], correspond to first
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426 145 yield, half peak, three-quarters peak, and peak flexural capacity along the load-deformation
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432 147 Gombeda et al. [9] introduced these milestones for a one-way spanning non-loadbearing
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434 148 precast panel using the line support boundary condition assumption shown previously in Figure
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436 149 1b. Due to the idealized simple supports, such a panel exhibits an approximately bi-linear
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438 150 resistance to lateral pressure in which peak capacity occurs in the intended span direction. Panels
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440 151 with discrete connections may form an initial mechanism earlier in the load-deformation history
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442 152 followed by a stable secondary mechanism. For example, the ultimate strength of a panel can be
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451 153 reached due to initial two-way engagement of the panel, after which peak displacement is reached
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453 154 at a lower capacity (i.e. in the descending branch of the panel's resistance function) once the
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455 155 weaker of the two flexural directions progresses toward failure. For this reason, the peak
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457 156 displacement of the panel is used to represent the peak milestone in this paper. Comparisons of
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459 157 response limits for reinforced concrete flexural members according to USACE [8] and Gombeda
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461 158 et al. [9] are shown in Table 1. Both sets of response criteria will be used later in this paper to
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463 159 assess the flexural performance of panels with discrete connections.
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466 160 Both sets of response limits are compatible with the generalized SDOF analysis approach,
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468 161 in which the flexural strength, stiffness, and deformation ductility of an element under dynamic
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470 162 loading are defined by its resistance function. In current practice, the SDOF approach is
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472 163 traditionally conducted using simplified assumptions, including an elastic-perfectly-plastic (EPP)
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474 164 resistance function, idealized boundary conditions, and nominal material properties. However, the
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476 165 simplified EPP approach combined with the one-way vertical span assumption may lead to
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478 166 inaccurate predictions of precast panel performance when discrete connections are used. As
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480 167 discussed, the presence of discrete connections may complicate the actual deformation response
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482 168 of the component if unexpected bi-directional deformation occurs. For example, a panel with
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484 169 minimal reinforcement in the horizontal direction may result in a weaker mechanism orthogonal
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486 170 to the assumed one-way vertical span, leading to reduced overall flexural resistance. Conversely,
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488 171 bi-directional behavior that increases the panel's flexural resistance can reduce deformation and
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490 172 damage but cause higher reaction forces, which can overcome the design capacity of the
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175 Table 1. Flexural response limits for non-loadbearing precast concrete panels

Element Description	Damage Level	Response Limits		
		PDC [8]	Gombeda et al. [9]	Response Limit Used
Reinforced concrete flexural members with no shear reinforcing and tension membrane	Superficial			
	B1	$\mu=1$	First yield of reinforcement	First yield of reinforcement
	Moderate			
	B2	$\square=2^\circ$	1/2 Peak resistance	1/2 Peak displacement
	Heavy			
	B3	$\square=5^\circ$	3/4 Peak resistance	3/4 Peak displacement
	Hazardous			
	B4	$\square=10^\circ$	Peak resistance	Peak displacement
	Blowout			

176 **2.3 Review of Recent Experimental Tests**

177 Recent blast tests of non-loadbearing precast panels have integrated the one-way flexure
 178 assumption into their test protocols by providing full edge bearing support at either end of the
 179 tested panels [3,11–13]. Several recent studies [14,15] have performed large scale blast tests of
 180 non-loadbearing precast wall panels that are supported with discrete connections; however, the
 181 connection spacing was much smaller than the primary panel span, and the panels therefore
 182 responded primarily in one-way bending as assumed in Figure 1b. Despite this, the resulting crack
 183 patterns near the discrete connections (for example, at the bottom connections in **Error!**
 184 **Reference source not found.**a [14,15]) did show some mild bi-directional response due to the
 185 presence of the discrete connections. This behavior is also observed in other experimentally tested
 186 panels with point supports when subjected to out-of-plane loading [16,17]. To date, bi-directional
 187 response for realistic discrete connection spacing in full-scale cladding panels has not been directly

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188 examined. Blast testing on concrete panels to examine two-way flexural response has
189 predominantly provided continuous bearing support to all four edges [18,19] rather than using
190 discrete connections.

191 The previous tests by Cramsey and Naito [14] and Naito et al. [15] showed that discrete
192 connections designed for conventional design loads do not perform well when subjected to blast
193 demands. Weld fracture within tieback connections, buckling of tieback plates, and punching shear
194 failure of steel stud embed plates in the concrete panels can occur when these connections are not
195 properly detailed for blast design requirements as shown in Naito et al. [20] (**Error! Reference
196 source not found.**b-e). Blast-induced reaction loads will be heavily influenced by the governing
197 flexural mechanics and plastic mechanism in either one-way (vertical or horizontal) or two-way
198 bending due to the presence of discrete connections and varying bi-directional reinforcement.

199 Figure 3. Post-test photos of precast panels subjected to blast loading: (a) front and back face
200 [14,15], and (b-e) damage to different types of connections [20]
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619 **202 3 Model Validation**
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621 203 This study relies on fundamental mechanics (via validated FE models) to develop panel
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623 204 resistance functions that capture realistic response mechanisms and damage milestones for a panel
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626 205 with discrete connections. These load-displacement relationships could ultimately be implemented
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628 206 into the aforementioned dynamic SDOF analysis methodology for blast resistant design. The focus
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630 207 of this paper is the sensitivity of these load-displacement relationships to the presence of discrete
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632 208 connections. Implementation of these resistance function in an “enhanced” SDOF approach, which
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634 209 can be performed using the approach proposed previously by Gombeda et al. [9], will be the subject
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636 210 of future research.

638 211 The out-of-plane flexural performance of non-loadbearing precast concrete cladding panels
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640 212 with discrete connections is examined via nonlinear FE modeling in ABAQUS [21]. Before
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642 213 conducting a parametric study, the FE modeling approach is validated using load-deformation
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644 214 results from previous experimental tests of both one-way and two-way spanning non-load bearing
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646 215 reinforced concrete panels. The nonlinear resistance function for each panel was obtained using
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648 216 the ABAQUS/Explicit analysis module, which can facilitate numerical stability with non-linear
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650 217 material models for concrete and steel reinforcement. Quasi-static analyses were conducted using
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652 218 a relatively slow loading rate to allow for gradual ramping of applied loads with negligible inertial
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654 219 effects. Quasi-static behavior was verified by insuring that a maximum ratio of kinetic-to-strain
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656 220 energies of 10% is maintained throughout the analysis [21]. The panel is modeled using a three-
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658 221 dimensional homogenous shell element (type S4) which also allows for transverse shear
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660 222 deformations. The S4 element automatically assigns the type of shell as either thick or thin. Thick
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662 223 shell theory is considered when the panel thickness-to-span length ratio is larger than 1/15, and
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664 224 Kirchoff thin shell theory is used for smaller ratios [21]. All panels examined in this study met the
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675 225 latter requirement for thin shell behavior. Steel reinforcement is defined as a smeared uniaxial
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677 226 layer at a user-defined depth in the shell element. The nonlinear behavior through the thickness of
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680 227 a component is defined by introducing integration points to calculate section properties [21].
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682 228 Simpson's rule is used for the shell section integration with around eleven integration points
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684 229 through the thickness of the section, to capture non-linear behavior [21]. The shell elements were
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686 230 meshed with an approximately square discretization with maximum edge dimension of 10.16 cm
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688 231 (4 in). Both the number of integration points and the mesh size were determined to be sufficient
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690 232 via a preliminary convergence study using several of the validation cases.
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692 233 Concrete behavior is modeled using a concrete damage plasticity (CDP) model with a
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694 234 dilation angle of 36° and eccentricity of 0.1 [21]. The ratio of biaxial, σ_{b0} , to uniaxial compressive
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696 235 strength, σ_{c0} , is taken as 1.16 [21]. A yield function is used to account for concrete's different
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698 236 response in tension and compression. The ratio of the tensile to compression meridian that defines
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700 237 the yield function in the deviatoric plane, K_c , was assumed as $2/3$ [21]. The uniaxial stress-strain
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702 238 relationship for concrete in tension is defined as linear elastic up to the modulus of rupture, after
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704 239 which a smooth descending branch accounts for the progression of micro-cracking and mitigates
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706 240 numerical instability. This softening model is populated using Equation 1 per Belarbi and Hsu [22]
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708 241 where f_t and ε_t are the maximum tensile strength and corresponding strain; f_{cr} and ε_{cr} are the
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710 242 modulus of rupture and corresponding strain; and n represents the rate of weakening (taken as 0.6).
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712 243 Unless the value is provided in the experimental data, modulus of rupture was calculated using
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714 244 Equation 2 [23], where f'_c is the concrete compressive strength (in MPa) and λ is the aggregate
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716 245 modification factor (taken as 1.0 for normalweight concrete).
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719 246 The Popovics model [24] is used to define the uniaxial stress-strain relationship for
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721 247 concrete in compression. The modulus of elasticity, E_c , for concrete (in MPa) was calculated using
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Equation 3 [23], where γ_c (the unit weight for concrete) is assumed to be 22.78 kN/m³ (145 pcf) across all panel cases. Where needed, the elastic stiffness of the finite element model is calibrated to the initial stiffness of the experimental test specimen by multiplying the elastic modulus by an adjustment factor α . The value of α is bounded by the limits of the scatter in the experimental measurements that provide the basis for the ACI 318 elastic modulus design equation [25], which is shown below in Equation 3 [23]. This expression will be used for the parametric study later in this paper.

$$f_t = f_{cr} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{cr}}{\varepsilon_t} \right)^n \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$f_{cr} = 0.7\lambda\sqrt{f'_c} \text{ (in MPa)} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

$$E_c = \alpha \cdot 0.043 \gamma_c^{1.5} \sqrt{f'_c} \text{ (in MPa)} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

The FE modeling approach is validated against the results of four experimental studies that examined the semi-static response of reinforced concrete panels to out-of-plane flexural loading with no applied in-plane loading:

- Gombeda et al. [26] evaluated the behavior of one-way solid reinforced concrete panels with varying reinforcement subjected to a uniform out-of-plane pressure loading.
- Cashell et al. [27] examined the response of a two-way slab with continuous edge supports subjected to out-of-plane point loads that were uniformly spaced and of uniform magnitude.
- Both McNeice [16] and Sakka and Gilbert [17] examined the behavior of a two-way panel with point supports.

Figure 4 illustrates the experimental setup and cross-sections of each test specimen. Material properties for all tests are summarized in Table 2. The steel reinforcement stress-strain model used by Gombeda et al. [28] was obtained via tensile tests of mild steel reinforcement that were performed during that experimental program. Since similar data is not available for the other three

268 studies, their stress-strain relationships were conservatively assumed to be bilinear with an elastic-
 269 hardening response. The elastic modulus for steel reinforcement is assumed to be 200 GPa (29000
 270 ksi) for all cases. The properties for steel (such as yield stress, f_{sy} , and the tensile stress, f_{su} , and
 271 strain, ϵ_{su}) as well as the properties for concrete (such as compressive strength, f'_c , modulus of
 272 elasticity, E_c , and ultimate strain, ϵ_{cu}) are also summarized in Table 2. The concrete modulus of
 273 elasticity for Gombeda et al.[28], Cashell et al. [27], and McNeice [16] were initially calculated
 274 using Equation 3 and then calibrated to match the experimentally measured stiffness of the whole
 275 panel. As a result, the elastic moduli for these three cases were modified by an α -factor of 2/3. The
 276 concrete elastic modulus for Sakka and Gilbert [17] was directly provided in the test summary.
 277 The ultimate strain for concrete is calculated as a function of the modulus of elasticity and ultimate
 278 compressive strength per the Popovics model [24].

Table 2. Material properties of experimental specimens used for FE validation

Experiment	CONCRETE			STEEL			
	E_c (GPa)	f'_c (MPa)	ϵ_{cu} (%)	f_{cr} (MPa)	f_{sy} (MPa)	f_{su} (MPa)	ϵ_{su} (%)
Gombeda et al.[28]	22.35*	49.11	0.30**	3.78*	476	969	10.8
Cashell et at. [27]	19.0*	35.52	0.28**	3.10	550	589	2.5
McNeice [16]	19.89*	38.92	0.28**	3.37*	345	517*	10.0*
Sakka and Gilbert [17]	29.20	44.30	0.29**	3.61	600	641	2.2

*Assumed value based on ACI 318 [23]; not provided by the test summary

**Assumed value based on the Popovics model [24]; not provided by the test summary

Figure 4. Schematic of experimental specimens (dimensions in cm) tested by (a) Gombeda et al.[28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16] and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]

The FE results, experimental response, and component-specific milestones (see Table 1) for the four validation cases are plotted in Figure 5. The resistance, corresponding to the applied pressure on the panel, is plotted against the midpoint (i.e. maximum) displacement of each panels. The FE model predictions show good agreement with the experimentally measured response. IN particular, the peak displacement at flexural failure for the models of Gombeda et al. [28] and Sakka and Gilbert [17] closely match the experimental data. Marginal discrepancies are observed in the FE failure displacements for Cashell et al. [27] and McNeice [16], most likely due to the unavoidable use of assumed material properties. However, the computational resistance at peak is generally conservative relative to experimental data for all cases.

The FE deflected shapes for the four validation cases are presented in Figure 6. Note that for two of the specimens (Figure 6c and d), only a quarter of the panel is shown due to symmetry in both directions. The FE model's deflected shape at peak milestone for Sakka and Gilbert [17]

295 is also compared with deformation contours captured during experimental testing and compares
 296 well to the results of the FE model as shown in Figure 6d. These results demonstrate the ability of
 297 this modeling approach to capture realistic mechanics of reinforced concrete panels.

298 (a)

(b)

299 (c)

(d)

300 Figure 5. Comparison of FE resistance functions with experimental test data from (a) Gombeda
 301 et al. [28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16], and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]

302 Figure 6. Deflected shapes (all dimensions in cm) of FE models representing (a) Gombeda et al.
 303 [28], (b) Cashell et al. [27], (c) McNeice [16] and (d) Sakka and Gilbert [17]

305 **4 Parametric Studies**

306 The validated FE model is used to examine changes in the flexural resistance functions and
 307 limit states of blast-resistant cladding panels due to varying discrete connection arrangements and
 308 cross-section design parameters. The parametric study is based on a generic prototype wall panel
 309 measuring 9.14 m (30 ft.) long by 4.57 m (15 ft.) tall (i.e. one story height per Figure 1a) with a
 310 thickness of 15.24 cm (6 in.). The wall panel is designed for conventional loads including wind,
 311 stripping, shipping/handling, and erection in accordance with the PCI Design Handbook [5]. The
 312 geometries and cross-section details of the panel are shown in Figure 7. The vertical bar size is not
 313 labeled because the reinforcement ratio in that direction is varied as part of the parametric study.
 314 The vertical reinforcement of the baseline prototype panel, designed for conventional loads,
 315 consists of #13 Grade 420 (#4 Grade 60) bars spaced at 39.37 cm (15.5 in.) on center for both the
 316 top and bottom layers. Horizontal reinforcement is designed for shrinkage and temperature

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317 requirements [23] and consists of #10 Grade 420 (#3 Grade 60) bars spaced at 45.7 cm (18.0 in.)
318 on center.

319 Material properties used for the FE model in the parametric study are summarized in Table
320 3, and example stress-strain models for concrete and steel are plotted in Figure 8a and b,
321 respectively. The same concrete model used for the validation study (see Section **Error!**
322 **Reference source not found.**) is implemented herein, and a typical compressive strength of 34.47
323 MPa (5000 psi) is assumed in all cases. The stress-strain relationship for steel reinforcement is
324 based on tensile test data from Gombeda et al. [28] and is scaled to match the minimum
325 requirements for yield strength, tensile strength, and ultimate tensile strain per ASTM A615 [29].
326 The conventionally assumed elastic-perfectly-plastic stress-strain design curve for steel
327 reinforcement [1] is also shown in Figure 8b for comparison.

328
329 Figure 7. Generic precast panel configuration (all dimensions in cm) for parametric evaluation

330 Table 3. Material properties of the parametric FE models,

CONCRETE				STEEL		
E_c (GPa)	f'_c (MPa)	ϵ_{cu} (%)	f_{cr} (MPa)	f_{sy} (MPa)	f_{su} (MPa)	ϵ_{su} (%)
28.09	34.47	0.18	3.66	413.69	620.53	9.0

331 (a) (b)
 332 Figure 8. Stress-strain relationships for (a) concrete and (b) reinforcing steel used in the
 333 validation and parametric FE models

334 **4.1 Varying Connection Spacing**

335 The panels are analyzed with six (6DC) and eight (8DC) evenly spaced discrete
 336 connections as shown in Figure 9 – both of these configurations are commonly used in precast
 337 construction. Also shown are the idealized spans and boundary conditions for one-way SDOF
 338 calculations of blast resistance in the vertical ($w1$) and horizontal ($w2$) flexural directions [30].
 339 Similar to Figure 1b, the idealized boundary conditions in Figure 9 are assumed as continuous
 340 supports that run through all connections in the same vertical or horizontal line (i.e. the connections
 341 are often assumed in practice to provide adequate stiffness across these lines such that the idealized
 342 boundary condition can be reasonably applied). Using the validated FE approach, models of the
 343 discrete connection configurations will be compared to those using the idealized one-way flexural
 344 assumptions for the vertical and horizontal axis directions to evaluate the applicability of the
 345 idealized approach.

Figure 9. Variation in discrete connection spacing (units in cm) for parametric study

4.2 Varying Ultimate Flexural Resistance in the Vertical Direction

Table 4 shows the variations of bi-directional ultimate flexural capacity that are considered in this study. Reinforcement in the $w1$ direction is varied while $w2$ is held constant at 6.26 kPa (0.91 psi) or 14.13 kPa (2.09 psi) (corresponding to the ACI 318 minimum for temperature and shrinkage effects [23]) for both the 6DC and 8DC cases. Reinforcement ratio is calculated using Equation 4 where A_s corresponds to the area of the extreme tension reinforcing steel; d is the distance from the extreme concrete compression fiber to the center of the extreme tensile steel reinforcement; and b is the bar spacing. Table 4 summarizes the reinforcement configurations considered in this study. As shown in Figure 7, the doubly reinforced cross-section utilizes the same rebar arrangements for the top and bottom layers. It is assumed that the precast concrete walls in this study are exposed to weather and manufactured under controlled plant conditions, and thus the clear cover for all rebar is set at 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) in accordance with ACI 318-14 [23].

As shown in Table 4, the range of vertical (primary) ultimate resistance is increased from 7.61 kPa to 52.31 kPa, thus increasing or “hardening” the panel’s lateral resistance per the idealized vertical span assumption in Figure 1b. The nominal moment capacity and net tensile strain are calculated via strain compatibility analysis considering both layers of reinforcement. The reinforcement near the compression face is subjected to low levels of tension at nominal capacity

and is included in the flexural strength calculations for completeness but is neglected when calculating the reinforcement ratio since its contribution is low and most designers would not include it for simplicity. The reinforcement ratio is therefore computed using only the extreme tension steel. The lowest vertical ultimate resistance is chosen such that the ratio of the nominal, M_n , to cracking moment, M_{cr} , using gross section properties is slightly greater than 1. The largest vertical ultimate resistance corresponds to a net tensile strain, ϵ_t , equal to 0.005 (i.e. the lower limit for tension controlled sections in accordance with ACI 318-14 [23]) in the extreme tension reinforcement at the nominal flexural capacity.

Table 4. Matrix of vertical (primary) ultimate flexural resistance used for parametric study

Bar size	#10 (#3)	#13 (#4)	#13 (#4)	#16 (#5)	#16 (#5)
d (cm)	12.86	12.7	12.7	12.54	12.54
b (cm)	28.58	39.37	30.48	15.24	7.62
ρ (%)	0.19	0.25	0.33	1.04	2.09
ρ_T (%)	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13
ϵ_t	0.040	0.030	0.023	0.007	0.005
M_n (kN-m)	136.61	177.45	225.0	522.94	938.4
M_n/M_{cr}	1.05	1.36	1.74	4.0	7.25
wI (kPa)	7.61	9.89	12.53	29.14	52.31
wI/w_2 (6DC)	1.22	1.58	2.00	4.66	8.36
wI/w_2 (8DC)	0.54	0.70	0.89	2.07	3.71

$$\rho = \frac{A_s}{b \cdot d} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Figure 10 shows the correlation of net tensile strain with allowable support rotation for a one-way reinforced concrete wall panel at the critical response milestones per Gombeda et al [28]. For higher values of ϵ_t (greater than 0.055), the cross-section behaves somewhat similarly to an unreinforced concrete cross-section, which exhibits a brittle failure mechanism limited by the tensile capacity of the concrete. Due to the shallow neutral axis depth, c , the small quantity of steel reinforcement rapidly accrues tensile strain prior to developing a fully-cracked section. This results in low ductility at all limit states as the peak flexural capacity is reached near the onset of flexural cracking. At ϵ_t just below 0.055, the maximum ductility is achieved via tension-controlled section

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382 behavior while approaching the maximum theoretical utilization of the steel reinforcement. As ϵ_t
383 continues to decrease, the likelihood of compression-controlled section behavior increases as the
384 neutral axis depth continues to move downward, thus accruing strain in the extreme concrete
385 compression fiber more rapidly than in the tension reinforcement. The section will experience
386 concrete crushing before the tensile capacity of the reinforcement can be significantly utilized,
387 resulting in decreased ductility. Several cross-sections with varying net tensile strain will be
388 examined in this study to examine whether the aforementioned observations also apply to two-
389 way spanning panels with discrete connections.

390
391 Figure 10 - Critical limit states and dominant response mechanisms as a function of net tensile
392 strain

393 4.3 Varying Connection Restraints

394 As shown previously in Figure 2, several different types of discrete connections are used
395 to attach cladding panels to the structural system of a building, and these connections can be
396 arranged to create a variety of boundary conditions for the panel. For example, tieback connections
397 can be arranged to act as roller with no translational restraint in either the vertical or horizontal
398 direction. The orthogonal non-roller direction could be idealized as either a pin or stiff translational

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399 spring. In the parametric study to follow, three possible boundary condition variations are
400 considered for the six connection (6DC) panel. BC1 is shown in Figure 11a where tieback
401 connections are arranged to allow thermal expansion in the horizontal direction and resist
402 translation in the vertical (primary) flexural direction. This case provides an idealized
403 representation of the typical tieback orientation used in practice. In Figure 11b, BC2 shows a
404 tieback orientation that instead allows expansion along the vertical axis. In Figure 11c, BC3 shows
405 an idealized case where tieback connections would allow translation in both the vertical and
406 horizontal directions (i.e. resembling a true simply supported panel). BC2 and BC3 represent
407 boundary conditions that are less feasible in practice but are included here to examine the influence
408 of in-plane connection restraint. Note that for all assumed boundary conditions, additional bearing
409 connections along the top of the panel would be installed to support the gravity loads. It is
410 commonly assumed that the bearing connections would not influence the response of the panel to
411 lateral loading; however, their participation in lateral resistance could be a consideration for future
412 research on this topic.

413
414 Figure 11. Idealized support conditions for parametric FE analysis of 6DC panels (units in cm)

5 Results

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416 The parametric analyses are labeled as follows: the first parameter denotes the number of
417 discrete connections in a panel (6DC and 8DC as shown in Figure 9); the second parameter shows
418 the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal ultimate resistance (e.g. $w1/w2 = 1.58$ for 6DC as shown in Table
419 4); and the third parameter denotes the type of boundary conditions (BC1, BC2 and BC3 as shown

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420 in Figure 11). The initial focus will evaluate the out-of-plane flexural performance of the 6DC
421 panels, which represent the most common connection configuration used in practice. Then the
422 analyses will evaluate the out-of-plane flexural performance of panels with 8DC.

423 **5.1 Panels with Six Discrete Connections (6DC)**

424 **5.1.1 Connection rotational stiffness**

425 Note that all lateral connections to this point have been represented in the FE model as a
426 translational restraint (with no rotational restraint) at a single node. Connections in precast
427 cladding construction are conventionally fabricated by embedding plates in the inside surface of
428 the panel via cast-in steel studs or other mechanical or post-installed anchorages. Although
429 connections are often idealized as a point support in design models, the true physical size of the
430 plate embed may provide a small amount of localized rotational resistance in addition to lateral
431 resistance. Selective preliminary analyses were performed prior to the full parametric study with
432 lateral connections represented with translational restraint at either one node or at four neighboring
433 nodes (i.e. assuming an embed plate size of 10.16 cm by 10.16 cm (4 in by 4 in)). The idealized 4-
434 node restraint was used to represent an upper bound for the development of localized moment
435 resistance by eliminating connection rotation at the shell element surrounded by the four supported
436 nodes (i.e. representing a “rotationally rigid” embed plate). This numerical representation provides
437 much higher rotational stiffness than a realistic embed connection, which would have low
438 rotational stiffness at its interface with the bolts or welded plates that connect the embed to the
439 structural system. The analysis is performed only for the conventionally designed panel with 6DC
440 and BC1 ($6DC-w1/w2=2-BC1$) for preliminary evaluation. A fourth parameter is added to the
441 reference labeling system for “large” boundary conditions (LBC) to identify cases in which the
442 connections are represented with a 4-node lateral restraint instead of single node lateral restraint.

Figure 12a compares the plots of semi-static load-displacement response obtained from FE analysis of the $6DC-w1/w2=2-BC1$ model with single node and 4-node (LBC) connections. The plotted lateral displacement represents the maximum overall panel displacement measured approximately midway between the connections as shown in Figure 12b. The component-specific limit states (see Table 1) are also plotted for each case. As expected, the presence of additional rotational restraint at the connections provides $\sim 25\%$ more out-of-plane flexural resistance and slightly greater deformation ductility. As noted previously, realistic connections will exhibit low rotational stiffnesses that more closely resemble the single supported node; therefore, the remaining analyses are conservatively conducted using the point support simplification.

Figure 12. Preliminary evaluation of connection rotational stiffness: (a) resistance functions and (b) deflected panel shapes with single node and “large” 4-node lateral supports (units in cm)

5.1.2 Resistance functions and deflected shapes for 6DC

Resistance functions and deflected shapes are obtained using the validated FE model for all 6DC configurations (see Table 4 and Figure 9a) for all three boundary conditions (BC1, BC2 and BC3 as shown in Figure 11). Figure 13 shows the deflected shape of each case at the peak

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459 displacement limit state. Figure 14a plots the resulting resistance functions as out-of-plane pressure
460 versus maximum displacement. Figure 14b normalizes the y-axis of these plots relative to the
461 maximum flexural resistance of the vertical w/l direction assuming the idealized horizontal line
462 connections (Figure 1b) per conventional design practice. Component-specific limit states and
463 prescriptive antiterrorism response limits for a flexural reinforced concrete member (with no shear
464 reinforcement and without tension membrane action [8]) are plotted as vertical dashed lines B1
465 through B4 in Figure 14 for comparison.

Figure 13. Peak FE deflected shapes for the 6DC panels (units in cm)

468 (a)

469 (b)

470 Figure 14. Out-of-plane flexural resistance of the 6DC panels: (a) load-displacement resistance
471 functions and (b) normalized to w_1

472 For BC1 (which is most representative of current practice), flexural behavior at peak
473 displacement was governed by the weaker reinforcement in the horizontal (w_2) direction for all
474 w_1/w_2 ratios that were considered. As a result, all cases with BC1 exhibit similar deformation at
475 peak since the horizontal reinforcement remained unchanged. Peak displacements for BC3 (with
476 no in-plane translational restraint at the connections) are almost identical to those for BC1, with
477 only the smallest w_1/w_2 ratios showing minor signs of two-way bending. If the tieback connections
478 instead allow vertical in-plane translation and restrain the horizontal translation (BC2), the flexural
479 capacity becomes governed by the vertical reinforcement if $w_1/w_2 \leq 2.0$. As shown in both Figure
480 13 and Figure 14, achieving a mechanism in the vertical direction enables increased deformation

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1627 481 ductility versus the horizontal mechanisms. With further increases in vertical reinforcement, the
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1629 482 BC2 connection configuration will also exhibit a horizontal mechanism with lower ductility, as
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1632 483 was shown for BC1 and BC3.
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1634 484 As shown in Figure 14, BC2 cases with $w1/w2$ of 1.58 and 2.0 achieved by far the largest
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1636 485 peak ductility, with peak displacements extending past the conventional B4 response limit to
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1638 486 achieve “blowout” damage per the prescribed PDC blast design criteria in Table 1. The BC2 case
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1640 487 with $w1/w2 = 1.22$ has less ductility (nearly reaching the B3 response limit to achieve “hazardous”
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1642 488 damage) due to the decrease in vertical reinforcement. All other cases, governed by horizontal
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1646 490 damage. The horizontal direction not only has less reinforcement than the vertical direction but
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1648 491 also has stiffer boundary conditions due to its continuity across the vertical centerline between the
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1650 492 two horizontal spans (whereas the vertical span can rotate freely at both ends). A plastic
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1654 494 increment of deflection versus a mechanism in the vertical span.
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1657 495 When the flexural resistance is normalized by the conventionally assumed one-way
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1659 496 capacity in the vertical direction, Figure 14b shows that only BC2 panels with $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$ and
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1661 497 BC1 panels with $w1/w2 \leq 1.58$ are able to surpass the $w1$ peak flexural capacity. These BC2 cases
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1663 498 exceed the idealized $w1$ resistance since their flexural response is consistent with the vertical one-
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1665 499 way design expectation at lower $w1/w2$ ratios. The BC1 cases exceed the idealized $w1$ resistance
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1667 500 only because the $w2$ resistance at very low $w1/w2$ ratios is similar to that in the $w1$ direction.
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1670 501 *5.1.3 Strain energy for 6DC*

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1672 502 The dynamic resistance of a structural component can be characterized by computing the
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1674 503 strain energy as the area under the resistance function up to a response limit of interest. For
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504 example, Figure 15 shows the strain energy of both the FE and the UFC resistance functions for a
505 $6DC-w1/w2=1.58-BC1$ panel up to their respective B3 response limits (i.e. the transition between
506 heavy and hazardous damage per Table 1). A model with larger value of strain energy for a
507 particular damage state implies a higher resistance to impulsive blast-induced pressure loading.
508 Figure 15 clearly shows that decreased ductility at similar damage states in the FE model versus
509 its UFC counterpart can lead to marked decreases in calculated blast resistance.

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511
512 Figure 15. Example strain energies calculated for (a) FE and (b) UFC resistance functions up to
513 the B3 limit.

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515 Figure 16 compares the strain energy calculated using FE and UFC resistance functions for
516 6DC panels with the BC1 and BC2 connection configurations. For the BC1 connections, Figure
517 16a reveals that both approaches achieve similar strain energies at the B1 yield milestone for panels

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518 with smaller $w1/w2$ ratios. For higher damage levels and larger $w1/w2$, the UFC approach (which
519 assumes vertical one-way flexural behavior) overestimates the amount of strain energy for all BC1
520 cases because the horizontal span direction controls the FE response (and thus reduces deformation
521 ductility and peak capacity). In Figure 16b for the BC2 panels, the UFC results show similar
522 overestimation of strain energy for damage states above B1 for larger $w1/w2$ ratios. At $w1/w2 \geq$
523 4.66, the FE response is again controlled by the weaker horizontal spans, resulting in losses of
524 available ductility and blast-resisting capacity. When the BC2 response achieves a vertical span
525 condition for $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$, the UFC strain energy is conservative relative to the FE results, which
526 accounts for realistic post-yield hardening as opposed to the UFC's elastic-perfectly-plastic
527 assumption.

528
529 Figure 16. Correlation of UFC and FE strain energies for 6DC panels with BC1 (solid scatter)
530 and BC2 (open scatter)

531 *5.1.4 Reactions for 6DC*

532 The out-of-plane connection reactions from the FE panel models with 6DC and BC2 are
533 compared to those based on the UFC approach [1], in which reaction demands, r , are based on the
534 relative tributary area of the connection per Figure 1a and b via Equation 5:

$$r = w1 \times \text{Tributary Area}$$

Equation 5

Figure 17 plots the FE reaction for the discrete connections at both the edge and middle of the panel as a function of maximum panel displacement. A comparison between the UFC approach and the peak FE reaction of the middle connection is shown in Figure 17b. For $w1/w2 \leq 2.0$, the cases fall above the bisecting line, which demonstrates that the UFC approach underpredicts the expected peak reaction force due to its elastic-perfectly-plastic resistance assumption. At $w1/w2 \geq 4.66$, the UFC reaction (based on the assumed vertical span response) is conservative since the FE response is controlled by the weaker horizontal spans and develops a smaller reaction. This comparison demonstrates that accurate determination of reaction design loads is depends on appropriate characterization of the mode of flexural resistance.

Figure 17. Connection reactions for 6DC-BC2 panels: (a) FE reactions versus displacement, and (b) correlation of FE and UFC reactions at the middle connection

5.2 Panels with Eight Discrete Connections (8DC)

5.2.1 Resistance functions and deflected shapes for 8DC

Increasing the number of discrete connections from six (6DC) to eight (8DC) per Figure 9b with no change in reinforcement leads to smaller $w1/w2$ ratios than the 6DC panels as shown in Table 4 due to the reduced effective horizontal span length. Using BC1, the deformed shapes at

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552 the peak displacement milestone are presented in Figure 18. Note that panel $8DC-w1/w2=3.71-$
 553 $BC1$ is not shown since it closely resembles the behavior observed for panel $8DC-w1/w2=2.07-$
 554 $BC1$. The FE resistance functions, shown in Figure 19, are normalized to the $w1$ UFC resistance
 555 and plotted against the maximum displacement at peak response. Similar to previous results, both
 556 figures show that configurations with higher $w1/w2$ result in plastic mechanisms in the horizontal
 557 direction while decreasing $w1/w2$ trends toward the preferred vertical floor-to-floor response
 558 mechanism. Specifically, the FE capacity is higher than the UFC resistance for all panels with
 559 $w1/w2$ less than 1.0. However, all FE resistance functions again develop comparable response
 560 limits at lower displacements than prescribed by the USACE criteria [8] in Table 1.

562 Figure 18. FE model deflected shapes at peak displacement for 8DC-BC1 panels (units in cm)

564 Figure 19. Resistance functions normalized to $w1$ for 8DC-BC1 panels

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5.2.2 Strain energy for 8DC

Figure 20 presents the relative strain energy calculated using the FE and UFC resistance functions for panels with 8DC and BC1. Since the preferred vertical one-way mechanism occurs in the FE models when $w1/w2 < 1.0$ (see Figure 18), these cases produce larger strain energy than the UFC resistance functions at comparable response limits. These results are very similar to the 6DC panel cases and suggest that increasing only the vertical reinforcement can produce significantly less strain energy (and thus less blast resistance) for discretely connected panels than would be expected under the UFC approach. As will be shown in Section 6, accompanying increases in horizontal reinforcement or the addition of other reinforcement detailing can help the panel achieve a preferred ductile mechanism.

Figure 20. Correlation of the UFC approach and the FE strain energies for 8DC-BC1 panels

5.2.3 Reactions for 8DC

The reaction forces for both the edge and middle connections of the 8DC panels with BC1 are shown in Figure 21a. In Figure 21b, the FE maximum reaction is compared to the UFC $w1$ reaction as was done in Section 5.1.4 for the 6DC panels. The UFC approach again underestimates peak reaction forces due to the use of realistic material hardening for panels that show the vertical

583 FE mechanism (for $w1/w2$ less than 1.0). For $w1/w2$ greater than 1.0, the transition of the FE
 584 flexural response from a stronger vertical to a weaker horizontal mechanism again produces
 585 smaller reaction forces versus the UFC approach.

586 (a) 587 Figure 21. Connection reactions for 8DC-BC1 panels: (a) FE reactions versus displacement, and
 588 (b) correlation of FE and UFC reactions at the middle connection

589 6 Alternative Detailing Strategies

590 6.1 Increased horizontal flexural resistance

591 The parametric study results showed that most of the panels with discrete connections and
 592 larger ratios of vertical-to-horizontal ultimate resistance exhibited a weaker flexural mechanism in
 593 the horizontal direction. Corresponding reductions in ductility lead to overestimation of the
 594 available strain energy (and thus the blast resistance) by the conventional UFC approach at
 595 comparable damage milestones. This section investigates the ratio of $w1/w2$ that will produce the
 596 preferred vertical flexural mechanism, using the 6DC panel with BC1 as a representative example.
 597 The vertical resistance ($w1$) is held constant per the $w1/w2=1.58$ 6DC case in Table 4, while the

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598 horizontal reinforcement (and thus w_2) is increased beyond the minimum requirements for
599 temperature and shrinkage.

600 Table 5 summarizes the new arrangements of horizontal reinforcement and the
601 correspondingly updated ratios of w_1/w_2 . The deflected shapes at peak deformation are also shown
602 in Figure 22. A transition from a dominant horizontal mechanism to bi-directional response is
603 observed with decreasing w_1/w_2 . With a w_1/w_2 ratio of 0.5, the behavior of the panel approaches
604 a one-way dominant mechanism in the intended vertical direction. Consistent with the deformed
605 shapes, Figure 23 reveals improvements in both flexural capacity and ductility as w_1/w_2 decreases.
606 Compared to the 8DC results (which achieved the ductile vertical mechanism at w_1/w_2 less than
607 1.0), these results suggest that increasing the aspect ratio of vertical-to-horizontal span length by
608 introducing more lateral connections may offer a more efficient solution for increasing the panel's
609 blast resistance.

610 Table 5. Upgraded arrangements of horizontal (transverse) reinforcement

Cases	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.9-BC1$	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.77-BC1$	$6DC-w_1/w_2=0.5-BC1$
Bar size and spacing	#10 @ 25.4 cm o.c.	#13 @ 39.37 cm o.c.	#13 @ 24.13 cm o.c.

Figure 22. FE deflected shape at peak deformation for the 6DC-BC1 panels with enhanced horizontal reinforcement (units in cm)

Figure 23. Out-of-plane flexural resistance curve of the strengthened panel

6.2 Enhanced edge reinforcement

As an alternative to increasing the horizontal flexural reinforcement, localized regions of edge reinforcement can be added to encourage the formation of the preferred vertical mechanism. Additional edge reinforcement is often added to precast cladding panels in practice to enhance structural integrity and reduce edge cracking in response to stripping and handling. In this case, the additional edge reinforcement consists of two #16 Grade 420 (#5 Grade 60) bars in the horizontal direction which are placed 10.16 cm (4.0 in.) above and below the centerlines of the connections shown in Figure 7. Figure 24 shows the deformed shape at the peak milestone for this panel and exhibits a much more prominent bi-directional response relative to the control panel. Although this detailing strategy does not facilitate a pure one-way failure mechanism, the resistance function demonstrates improvements in both flexural capacity and ductility as shown in Figure 25 by engaging both flexural directions.

Figure 24. Peak deflected shapes for modified edge reinforcement panels

Figure 25. Resistance functions for panels with additional edge reinforcement

7 Summary and Conclusions

A numerical study of solid (i.e. non-insulated) precast concrete cladding panels was conducted to examine the influence of discrete connections on load-deformation response under out-of-plane loads. The study is conducted using a nonlinear finite element (FE) modeling approach that is validated against the results of four experimental studies by other researchers. The validated model was used to conduct a series of parametric studies which varied the number of discrete connections and the amount of reinforcement in both the vertical and horizontal directions. The numerical responses are also compared to standard blast design assumptions which incorporate nominal material properties and idealized elastic-perfectly-plastic response. Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

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- 642 • In current practice, panels with discrete connections are often designed for blast loading by
643 assuming one-way vertical flexural resistance between floor diaphragms. The horizontal spans
644 are designed with minimum reinforcement and are assumed to contribute little to the panels’
645 blast resistance. However, increasing only the vertical resistance in response to blast loading
646 requirements may induce an unexpected failure mechanism in the weaker horizontal direction
647 depending on the aspect ratio of vertical-to-horizontal span between connections, thus leading
648 to significant reductions in flexural capacity and ductility.
- 649 • Strain energies calculated for these horizontal mechanisms were significantly smaller than
650 those calculated for the conventional design approaches, which assumed the more ductile
651 vertical mechanism. Lower strain energy indicates lower blast resistance due to less energy
652 absorption in response to impulsive loading.
- 653 • Response limits corresponding to progressive states of flexural damage were calculated for
654 each panel configuration based on material properties and the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal
655 ultimate flexural resistance. Significant discrepancies between these tailored response limits
656 and current prescriptive blast response criteria were observed, especially for panels exhibiting
657 a premature weak direction failure mechanism. Many panel cases demonstrated significantly
658 less ductility at elevated levels of flexural damage compared with the prescriptive criteria.
- 659 • The FE models with discrete connections were able to achieve a vertical mechanism by either
660 decreasing the ratio of vertical-to-horizontal flexural capacity and/or increasing the number of
661 lateral connections (thereby reducing the horizontal span between these connections). For
662 panels with vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios near 1.0, a vertical-to-horizontal flexural
663 capacity ratio of 0.5 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism. For panels with

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664 vertical-to-horizontal span aspect ratios greater than 1.5, a vertical-to-horizontal flexural
665 capacity ratio of only 1.0 was needed to develop the vertical plastic mechanism.

- 666 • Bi-directional flexural behavior and realistic material properties often result in reaction forces
667 significantly larger than predicted using the conventional assumption of vertical one-way
668 flexure. This implies that connections may need to be strengthened to realistically develop the
669 peak flexural capacity of the component.
- 670 • Localized additions of reinforcement near the panel edges can facilitate improvements in
671 flexural capacity and ductility for reinforcement and connection configurations that would
672 otherwise form the weak direction failure mechanism.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author Statement

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